

PLANNING THESIS ON

**STRATEGY FOR BETTER PUBLIC TRANSPORTATION : A CASE OF HYDERABAD
METROPOLITAN DEVELOPMENT AREA**

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**BACHELOR OF TECHNOLOGY (URBAN AND
REGIONAL PLANNING)**

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METROPOLITAN DEVELOPMENT AREA**

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for the award of the degree of **Bachelor of Technology (Planning)** of this

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Abstract

Public mobility plays a very significant role in day to day activities of every individual. In the present scenario of over population and urban crowds the preferable means of transportation in terms of users experience is individual vehicles above public transportation. This scenario in the long run would be a critical threat for the World agenda of achieving sustainable development goals. There is a need to explore options for a better and sustainable future. The main key aspect would be improving public transportation in terms of public satisfaction. In an approach to this scenario the fusion of various technological advances gave rise to a privileged alternative which is Intelligent public transport systems which helps authorities in traffic management and individuals in improving proficient decisions in usage of public transport with respect to their comfort levels where this would increase the efficiency of public transportation and lead a way towards sustainable future.

Declaration

I here declare that this thesis is a presentation of my original research work, wherever contributions of others are involved. Every effort is made to indicate this clearly, with the references to the literature, and acknowledgement of collaborative research and discussion. The work was done under the guidance of Mrs Mounika, at Department of Urban and Regional Planning of the Jawaharlal Nehru Architecture and Fine Arts University, Hyderabad. I certify that the above statements are true to the best of my knowledge.

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Acronyms

HMDA	Hyderabad Metropolitan development authority
DEA	Data Envelopment analysis
ITS	Intelligent transport systems
MMTS	Multimodal transport system
HMRL	Hyderabad Metro rail Limited
AQEI	Air quality exposure Index
LOS	Level of Service
TSRTC	Telangana state road transport corporation
BAU	Business Asual Scenario
PM	Particulate matter
UNESCAP	United nations Economic and social commission for asia and pacific
SDG	Sustainable development goal
IPA	Importance Performance Analysis
MOUD	Ministry of Urban development

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CHAPTER-1
INTRODUCTION

Introduction

Public transportation

Public transportation is a form of travel offered locally that enables more people to travel together along designated routes depending on various modes of public transportation. (Rinkesh)

From the concept given by UN habitat public transportation refers to “Shared passenger transport services that are available to the general public and which are provided for the public good. It may include cars, buses, trolleys, trams, trains, subways, and ferries that are shared by strangers without prior arrangement. It may also include informal modes of transport (para-transit) - but it is noted that these are often lacking in designated routes or stops. However, it excludes taxis, car pools, and hired buses, which are not shared by strangers without prior arrangement.” (UN habitat, 2021)

Basic modes of public transportation are:

Figure 1 Modes of public transportation

Significance

The sheer size of the world and the limited resources in one place have always meant that humans must travel outside of where they live, whether it's to get food, go to work, or for a social visit. Public transit provides efficiency and cost-savings for people traveling in the same direction or destination, as the cost is shared between everyone traveling.

Public transportation also helps to reduce road congestion and travel times, air pollution, and energy and oil consumption, all of which benefit both riders and non-riders alike.

History

The first form of public transport was multiple people riding animals. Animal-drawn ferries are thought to be the earliest form of public transit. The wheel was invented in 3,500 BC but it wasn't until 1,600 BC that it was used for a chariot. This is when the idea of longer distance travel was possible by road.

1820's

The first concept of a public transit system in a city started in the 1820's in France and London with the introduction of the omnibus, a horse-drawn car that held up to 10 people at a time. With the roads as they were in those days, can you imagine how uncomfortable that would have been?

In 1825 George Stephenson built the first public steam railway in the world, the locomotion between Stockton and Darlington railway in UK.

1830's

The first authenticated streetcar in America, the New York and Harlem railroad, began service in 1832. It wasn't until 1855 in Paris that the first permanent tram line in continental Europe was opened, 1858 in South America in Santiago, Chile, and 1860 in Sydney, Australia.

1880's

The first public electric tram line opened in Berlin, Germany in 1881. It initially drew current from the rails, with overhead wire being installed in 1883.

1890's

In 1890 the first underground railway in the form of the Metropolitan Railway on what would become the London Underground.

The first rapid transit system in the United States was built a few years later in 1892 in Chicago- the "L" train continues to run to this day.

Boston, Massachusetts opened the first subway system in the U.S in 1897 to avoid severe weather conditions.

1910

Another UK first occurred in 1910 when the 1st mass-produced bus was introduced in London. This double-decker style is still in place today.

1920's

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The introduction of the motorbus was in 1992 which rapidly changed the speed in which passengers were able to get to their destination.

1960's

The first bullet train was introduced in 1964 between Tokyo and Osaka in Japan. The average speed was 99mph

In the U.S in the 60's, steam trains transitioned to diesel-electric powered trains

2000's

Shanghai was the first city to implement battery buses- an electric bus that uses energy from on-board batteries to drive electric motor. These offer zero emission and are much quieter than normal buses. China had about 99 percent of the 3,85,000 electric buses on the roads worldwide its cities are adding 1900 electric buses per week. (Moovit, 2018)

Evolution of road transport sector in India

Starting from 1960's, Indian road network has developed in several stages and it is largely influenced by different political, technological, environmental and social factors. Total length of motorable roads in India in 1954 was estimated to be 353,000 kms, which was meagre for any country of size of India, and its population. In 1985, the total motorable road length increased to 1.77 million kms and 208,938 villages were connected by the new roads. The problems related to urban transport became increasingly complex due to massive increase in road network, increased economic activities on the one hand and shortage of resources on the other hand. Due to unprecedented growth in population and unchecked migration from rural areas to urban areas and metropolitan cities, population pressure increased in urban areas and metropolitan cities. (TECHNOLOGY INFORMATION,, 2016)

Present scenario

The rapid growth of India's urban population has put enormous strains on transport systems. Burgeoning travel demand for exceeds the limited supply of transport infrastructure and services. Public transport, in particular, has been completely overwhelmed. Most bus and train services are overcrowded, undependable, slow, inconvenient, uncoordinated, and dangerous. Moreover, the public ownership and

operation of most public transport services has greatly reduced productivity and inflated costs. India's cities desperately need improved and expanded public transport service. Unfortunately, meager government financial assistance and complete lack of any supportive policies, such as traffic priority for buses, place public transport in an almost impossible situation. (swamy, 2014)

Due to the nature of public transportation of serving public that cannot limit its functioning with respect to the comfort of single user. The comfortable option for the users is being opting private vehicles upon public transport systems.

Figure 2 Modal share 2011

Source : Transport and Communications Bulletin for Asia and the Pacific, M. Absar Alam and Faisal Ahmed, 2013

Figure 3 Modal share 2016

Source :Down to earth magazine, 2018

Figure 4 Count of Registered Private Vehicles and share of energy

Source: Centre for science and environment

Research problem

Due to various issues and concerns faced by an individual in terms of accessibility and efficiency the shift is been observed from public transportation to private transportation

Shift of major modal share to private when compared to public transportation is observed and this modal shift has greater impact on traffic scenarios leading various major serious traffic issues .along with environment depletion which creates a major barrier to achieve world agenda goals of sustainable development.

This issue of increase in private vehicles is multi-dimensional in nature

Issues of increase in private vehicles

Figure 5 Issue of increase in private vehicles

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These issues has severe impact on all direct transport targets of the sustainable development.

Major Traffic issues

The traffic issues raised by increase in private vehicles is being a major issue all over India's metropolitan cities.

Figure 6 Traffic issues due to private vehicles

Source : Private vehicles major cause of traffic jams, says BMC study, Hindustan times 2015

Pollutants emission

The level of emissions caused into environment in comparison of both public vehicles and automobiles understanding this relation would play a key role in understanding the seriousness of the issue

Figure 7 Pollutants emission

Source : Why Transit Matters: The Environmental Benefits of Public Transportation, acog, 2013

Congestion

Congestion is other major issue which is haunting the traffic scenarios in metropolitan cities of India . congestion has many causes one of the major cause is increase in vehicles.

Figure 8 Congestion due to vehicles

Source: Cars, bikes now occupy 77% of Mumbai roads, buses 2%, The times of India, 2018

Costs of travel

Costs of travel has an impact on mode of travel they choose the variation of these charges based on mode of transportation is shown in the figure below:

Figure 9 direct costs of urban travel

Source : Cost of Transit - Derived from (1999) Transportation for Livable Cities By Vukan R. Vuchic

These issues in the long run would lead to worst traffic scenarios which has direct affect on transportation performance and quality of life of people.

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The solutions prescribed by UN habitat for improving transportation conditions at a city level is to improve public transportation systems being 1st priority in their reforms

From the understanding of seriousness of this issue in developing countries like India gave a scope to research for betterment of traffic scenarios this gave rise to the main aim of the project so that the effectiveness of the solutions would play a key role in relief from traffic issues with respect to all dimensions such as health, environment and human well-being.

Review: National Clean Air Programme (NCAP) of India

NCAP was approved in 2019 with 122 cities from 20 states and 3 union territories designated as “non-attainment”. The programme is designed to document, in all the cities

- (1) emission and pollution load via monitoring and modelling
- (2) activities necessary for all the known sources to achieve 20-30% reduction in the ambient PM2.5 levels by 2024, when compared to 2017
- (3) plans to build institutional capacity to manage the information flow and
- (4) ways to oversee the progress of various components.

UrbanEmissions.Info is one of the organization to oversee the NCAP programme in india It stands for

- (a) sharing knowledge on air pollution
- (b) science based air quality analysis
- (c) advocacy and awareness raising on air quality management and
- (d) building partnerships among local, national, and international air-heads.

Its main agenda in reducing urban emissions is as follow:

Figure 10 controlling road transport emissions

Table 1 Direct development goals of sustainable development

Direct development goals of Sustainable development	
3.Ensure healthy lives and promote well-being for all at all ages (Road safety)	3.6 By 2020, halve the number of global deaths and injuries from road traffic accidents
7.Ensure access of affordable, reliable, sustainable and modern energy for all (energy efficiency)	7.3 By 2030, double the global rate of improvement in energy efficiency
9.Build resilient infrastructure, promote inclusive and sustainable industrialization and foster innovation (sustainable infrastructure)	9.1 Develop quality, reliable, sustainable and resilient infrastructure, including regional and trans-border infrastructure, to support economic development and human well-being, with a focus on affordable and equitable access for all
11. Make cities and human settlements inclusive, safe, resilient and sustainable (sustainable urban transport for all)	11.2 By,2030 provide access to safe, affordable, accessible and sustainable transport systems for all, improving road safety, notably by expanding public transport, with special attention to the needs of those in vulnerable situations, women, children, persons with disabilities and older persons

Source : Analysis of the transport relevance of each of the 17 SDGs, UN

Research project

Aim

Improving coverage and efficiency of public transportation

Research questions

In order to reach the aim of the project the requirement of set of research questions which provide a path motivation towards carrying out the research. In order to improve coverage and efficiency of public transportation basic framework questions are:

- What are the reasons behind opting private vehicles above public transportation?

Contribution: studying people based on their perceptions towards public transportation.

Significance: Studying people behavior and their perceptions is primary step for a planner to proceed with other activities.

- How to assess efficiency of public transportation?

Contribution: Understanding present quality of service provided by public transportation

Significance: understanding and analyzing present scenario effectively would provide with key aspects of understand loop holes causing inefficiency to the working mechanisms of the systems.

- What are efficient management systems for major mode of public transportation?

Contribution: Understanding efficiency improvement systems with respect to indian scenario would give scope to better performance there by increasing usage of public transportation

Significance: efficiency improving techniques are key aspects to reach the aim of the project which is encouraging people towards using public transportation.

Objectives:

- Knowing areas covered and uncovered under public transportation and incentives for development
- Efficiency Assessment of public transportation
- Understanding viable efficiency management systems
- Understanding public opinion with respect to functioning of public transportation.

Scope

The main focus is towards improving coverage and efficiency

- **Coverage** – with respect to Bus, HMRL and MMTS modes of transportation.
- **Efficiency** – with respect to proper functioning and improving user experience in using public transportation.

Limitation:

The study area is limited to HMDA region

Detailed methodology

Figure 11 detailed methodology

CHAPTER-2

Literature

Selection of study area

In an approach to select a study area the procedure of selection is been made into 3 steps

1. Considerations : This is where formulation of considerations which are required as attributes for the study area is framed
2. Conditions : evolving from the considerations conditions are framed which are main elements for selecting a study area
3. Tasks : taking these consideration and conditions taking them as criteria the appropriate study area is to be selected which is in the form of tasks

Considerations

Considerations of the study area with respect to research requirements

- The issue is dominantly observed in core area of major metropolitan cities.
- This modal shift has a great impact on transportation performance of the city.

From these considerations we would understand that the area which satisfies our considerations would be feasible to be selected as study area for the research

Conditions

From these considerations the conditions can be extracted

- ✓ It should be a major metropolitan cities
- ✓ It should have low transportation performance.

Tasks

In order to obtain the study area are tasks are required which are performed with respect to the conditions that are evolved for selection of study area

1. Selection of metropolitan city with low transportation performance
2. Core area of selected metropolitan city

Task-1

Selection of metropolitan city with low transportation performance

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Developing countries experience worst scenarios due to issues arise from over population in which one of the worst hit sectors is transportation. In order to know the situations understanding the transportation scenario of a developing and over populated country like India would be more appropriate.

Urban Transport scenario in India

The Transport scenario may differ in between cities based on their own circumstances but certain basic trends and the responsible factors for the trends remain same overall the country. A study was carried out by Ministry of urban development in order to understand the performance of Indian cities .this study approach comprised of 3 steps as follow:

Step 1: selection of cities: this selection was carried with respect to the following factors

- Size of city
- Shape of city
- Availability of Public Transport
- Economic Activity level of the city
- Congestion
- Geographical locations

Based on these factors 30 representative cities are considered for the study out of 87 cities which are qualified to be a part of study

Out of which major metropolitan cities are concentrated for site selection as our 1st criteria for selecting the site area is its nature of being a metropolitan city.

The Census Commission of India defines Metropolitan cities as those Indian cities having a population of more than 4 million

Metropolitan cities for study area selection are major metropiltan cities

- Delhi
- Mumbai
- Banglore
- Kolkata
- Hyderabad and Chennai

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Figure 12 Cities selected for study by MOUD

Source: Urban transportation scenario in india , Ministry of urban development

Step 2: Data collection from primary and secondary surveys. With respect to transportation was collected.

Step 3: has been the development of strategic

Transport models in order to establish the future urban transport scenario. These models are developed using software TRANSCAD/ CUBE.

Indices have been developed in order to evaluate the performance of transportation .These indices and the resultant performance of cities is presented below

. These are:

Sr. No.	Traffic indicators	Weightage
1.	Public transport accessibility	1
2.	Congestion	2
3.	Walkability	2
4.	City bus transport supply	2
5.	Safety	1.5
6.	On- street parking Interference	1
7.	Slow Moving Vehicle Index	2

Figure 13 Traffic indicators

The following graph is the resultant after analysis with respect to indices

Figure 14 Performance of cities

Out of which concentrated cities are been highlighted comparing performance of these major metropolitan cities lowest performance is observed in Hyderabad with score of 400.

Task-2

Core area of selected metropolitan city is taken as administrative boundary for the city growth which is boundary set by authority of HMDA.

Figure 15 Hyderabad

Literature review

A series of papers are been taken in order to review the literature study carried out on the topic of improving public transportation.

Paper-1 Analysis of urban public transportation network in Hyderabad: Telangana

Author

- gongalla vamsi krishna,
- ujjal chattaraj

Introduction:

The objectives of this study is to evaluate the existing public transportation network by some parameters like bus stop accessibility, average travel time, road network, number of transfers, waiting time, number of bus service trips and evaluation of road network in Hyderabad City.

- To understand what is the present situation of the public transport network of Hyderabad city is today and what will be in the future.
- To propose some upgradation lines and some new lines which can strengthen the urban public transportation of the Hyderabad road network.
 - To calculate transportation indices for every selected place in the study area and asses which route is to be updated to minimize the traffic problems.
 - To develop a model for bus network in view of future urban transportation development (integration of Bus network and MMTS).
 - To propose some options to improve the existing transportation network and finding the impact of options suggested over the existing bus network using macro simulation software tool VISUM.

Parameters and tools and techniques

Table 2 Parameters tools and techniques

Parameters	Tools and techniques
Modelling of public transport network	VISUM technology
Number of service trips	number of service trips per peak hour
Area coverage by public transportation	400m as approximate walking distance to the nearest transit station.
Travel time analysis to reach public transportation	Isochrones

Traffic parameters	Regression formulas used by ministry of
Accessibility index	Ministry of Housing and Urban Affairs to
Congestion index	find transportation performance index
Safety index	

Conclusion: In this study three modes of public transportation networks in Hyderabad is evaluated using VISUM software and transportation performance indices like Accessibility index, Congestion index, Safety index and Travel times analysis. Some options are suggested to improve the existing public transportation network based on studies done in this paper

Research gap

With respect to bus network the service trips and coverage is been shown least analyzed when compared to other modes

Aspects to inculcate in research

Area coverage by public transportation (GONGALLA VAMSI KRISHNA, 2020)

Paper-2 Innovative public transport information systems – A pilot study of Hyderabad

Author

Shakti sustainable energy foundation , June,2016

Introduction:

The general methodology developed to undertake this exercise has been structured in a generic manner and can be replicated for any other city in India. Survey methodology included ‘Flock Sourcing’ and types of data collected included Bus Stop Data, Bus route data and Schedule data. Around data for 82 routes (including 31 core corridors and other branches) has been collected.

- For data collection specialized smart phone based tools/app (RouteMaster) was developed.

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- A web based version was also created which would be more useful in analyzing the overall data with respect to the spatial issues. The web based version would be the foundation for creating the final app for users. Existing bus stops and schedules were mapped and visuals generated. Using the data collected from the app changed routes were also identified.
- GTFS feed was created accordingly.
- An important part of the exercise was to engage with the TSRTC. Discussions were held with the senior management like the Executive Director and Dy. Chief Traffic Manager regarding issues related to operations, data collection, technology use and willingness to test innovative Public Transport Information Systems (APP based). Interviews were conducted with the Union and the crew to understand the wide ranging issues affecting the functioning of the TSRTC and for a balanced view. Establishing relationships with the TSRTC on the use of data was an important achievement under this head. Another finding of this project is the need to develop relationships between various players in the society for knowledge sharing.
- The other thrust areas identified in this project which need to be focused on in the future are bringing in data efficiency with a focus on open transit data, developing an app for real time data, creation of authenticated static maps, creating infrastructure for real time tracking, developing multimodal public transit information systems. An important result is the achievement replicability of the app and dashboard.

Parameters, tools and techniques

Table 3 Parameters , tools and techniques

Parameters	Tools and Techniques
Transit data collection	Flock sourcing of data [App development] Crowd sourcing of data [Web based data input] for bustops ,routes

Research gap:

- Bringing in data efficiency
- App for real time data
- Creation of authenticated static maps
- Infrastructure for real time tracking
- Multimodal public transit information systems

Aspects to inculcate in research

- Web based input for public transport users for improving efficiency (Shakti foundation, 2016)

Paper-3 Evaluation of Public Transportation Operation Based on Data Envelopment Analysis

Author: Jiabin Lia , Xumei Chen^{b,c} , Xin Lib,c , Xiucheng Guoa, School of Transportation, Southeast University, Nanjing, Jiangsu, China,2013

Introduction: This paper presented method on evaluating the performance of bus routes within a public transportation system using revised DEA method and sensitivity analysis of indexes. First, based on the analysis of the operation of public transportation, passenger load rate, service reliability, average dwell time and average running speed were chosen as output indexes, a virtual index as input from operators and passenger perspective. The method is applied to bus routes in Beijing public transportation system and the improvement suggestions are put forward. Finally, the results which show that the operation in off-peak period are better than that in peak period, and average running time and service reliability are the key factors influencing performance, conform to the reality of the city, thus validating the practicality of the method. In sum, this study is helpful for improving the operation of public transportation system.

Parameters , tools and techniques

Figure 16 Parameters

Parameters	Tools and techniques
<ul style="list-style-type: none">• Service reliability• Passenger load rate• Average dwell time• Average running speed	<ul style="list-style-type: none">• DEA Analysis for efficiency

Research gap: detailing criteria for selection indexes and parameters

Conclusion: In this paper, the evaluation index system of public transportation operation is established by selecting four key indexes, including passenger load rate, service reliability, average dwell time, and average running speed. Then operation evaluation model are built and sensitivity analysis of indexes model are conducted. The case study shows that the method has good applicability, and can be used to improve the operation of public transportation system. Nevertheless, the DEA method has relative evaluation result. Hence, the route with a good evaluation result may still require improvements. This problem can be solved by adding evaluation objects or determining the index expectations using the Delphi method. (jia, 2013)

Paper-4 Performance Analysis of Sub Urban Rail System in Delhi - A Case Study

Author : Rahul Raoniara , Amudapuram Mohan Raob* , S. Velmuruganc CSIR-Central Road Research Institute, New Delhi110025, India

Introduction : Transportation facilities evolve day by day in all cities irrespective of their status. Delhi transportation system connectivity lies at par with major cities across the world. Public transit systems such as Metro; Bus and Rail are the most extensively used by the commuters on daily basis. The study aims to identify the service quality and performance gap in terms of user perception and to identify the major attribute that defines transit service performance.

Parameters

1. Personal Safety
2. onboard Personal Safety at Station

3. Cleanliness of Trains
4. Cleanliness of Station
5. Cleanliness of Toilet Facilities
6. Availability of Seats at Station
7. Crowding onboard
8. Comfort onboard
9. Electrical Equipment Functionality
10. Railway Fare
11. Frequency of Train
12. Regularity of Train
13. Parking Facilities
14. Facilities for Disabled person
15. Luggage facility onboard
16. Information Dessimination at Station
17. Timely Information
18. Announcement and Display
19. Complaint Registration
20. Ticket Inspection

Research gap

Spatial linkage with respect to functioning of sub-railway in terms of Location, population density and access towards station , external parameters in order to access the facilities.

Conclusion:

Results indicates the current passengers of Delhi's Suburban Rail system are not satisfied with the overall service quality provided. CSI value obtained is 0.45 which is quite low compared to the highest level of service quality measure i.e. ranges in between 0.81 to 1 and SEM analysis indicates, Delhi Suburban rail transit system isn't having a positive impact on passenger satisfaction in Delhi City.

Paper 5 Automatic Generation of Station Catchment Areas:

Author: Ting(Grace) Lin, Richard Palmer, Jianhong (Cecilia) Xia and David A. McMeekin Department of Spatial Sciences Curtin University,2014

Introduction:

A train station catchment area can be generated in two ways: by surveying train users or by modelling methods. The former method is time consuming and labor intensive. In this paper attention was given to develop methods that automatically generate station catchment areas. This study’s aim was to compare two modelling methods: the Euclidean distance transform / Voronoi diagram generation method and a location-allocation method for automatically generating station catchment areas. A case study of the Perth Metropolitan area, in Western Australia, was used to implement these two methods. The results from these two methods are consistent and the methods demonstrate robustness for understanding the nature of station catchment areas and provide useful insights for public transport planning in Perth.

Parameters tools and techniques

Parameters	Tools and Techniques
Catchment area characteristic analysis Applications of catchment area	- Circle generation methods - . location-allocation methods [Euclidean tools]

Figure 17 Parameters

Research gap: other factors, such as station location, travel modes, and train frequency discussed in the Background section, may also affect the station catchment area size

Conclusion : In summary, this study compared the two automatic catchment area generation methods: the Euclidian distance formation algorithm and the location-allocation methods. The results from these two methods were consistent and the methods were shown to be robust for understanding the nature of station catchment areas and will provide useful insight for public transportation planning in Perth (lin, 2014)

Overall Understanding on Literature review

The main concern with respect to perspective of all the research papers is to improve public transportation as to improve traffic conditions and for human wellbeing. With respect to research

papers, The Main aspect of improving public transportation is more over classified to 2 dimensional studies of

- Understanding opinions
- Improving data creation

Understanding opinions: Understanding opinions is the primary step for improvement of public transportation. Opinions are form of descriptions which could be understood in a general manner. But the main issue here is converting lexicon data to other forms those are reliable and assured data formats that could be extracted and used for further analysis. The concentration with respect to opinion analysis is towards exploring various methods and approaches in order to analyze opinions few techniques used in these are

Sentimental analysis

This is where the descriptive inputs given by the public transportation users is converted to mathematical formulas using which reliable values of understanding and further analysis is taking place

Linear regression based on results of survey

In this approach the inputs trough survey formats is taken as primary source for whole process where the received inputs are gathered and are analyzed using quantitative methods using median , deviation of the attained values whereas the linear regression model is applied for the data attaining scope of reliable and assured analysis.

Improving data creation: Data creation is other important aspect considered in this study because the inefficiency of proper data is assumed to be the root cause for rising problems with respect to public transportation. Improvement of data can give rise to multi-dimensional analysis resulting in better outcomes for the issues in an effective manner. Detail analysis of data is the key aspect for effective outcome. few techniques and aspects used to improving data are:

Mobile Applications

The apps are developed in order to improve data collection and also give access to the public in order to improve their user experience improving comfortability

Technical prediction models

This is where the computerized technical applications are developed to understand patterns of flow with respect to existing and sparse data availability concerns

In conclusion the researches have evolved to provide detail and keen analysis on inputs that are required to assess public transportation the importance of data structures and availability is reflected through these researches focusing on the improvement of the public transportation systems.

Literature Case study

In an approach to select a study area the procedure of selecting is been made into 3 steps

1. Considerations : This is where formulation of considerations which are required as attributes for the study area is framed
2. Conditions : evolving from the considerations conditions are framed which are main elements for selecting a study area
3. Tasks : taking these consideration and conditions taking them as criteria the appropriate study area is to be selected which is in the form of tasks

Considerations and conditions:

Aspects of selecting literature case study

- Major metropolitan city
- Best practise in Improving performance of public transportation
- Similarity in spatial characteristics with selected site for research

Major metropolitan cities

- Delhi
- Mumbai
- Chennai
- Banglore
- Kolkata

Best practices in improving public transportation

Excellence in urban transport awards under 14th urban mobility India conference 2021

- Metro rail with best passenger services and satisfaction
- 1st place Delhi metro rail corporation limited
- 2nd place Mumbai metro one private limited

Spatial characteristics

Table 4 Spatial characteristics

Similarity in spatial characteristics			
Site selected for Best practices study			
City	Hyderabad	Delhi	Mumbai
Spatial characteristics	Radial form	Radial form	Linear form
Similarity in spatial characteristics	<p>Delhi matches with the spatial characteristics with Hyderabad by its form of growth which is radial these spatial characteristics are important aspect for overall detail study of networks and implementations of solutions.</p>		

Selected desktop study- Delhi

City characteristics

Delhi is located in the heart of northern part of India. It has an area of 1,483 sq. km. It shares borders with the States of Uttar Pradesh and Haryana. The National Capital Territory (NCT) of Delhi comprises eleven (11) districts, twenty seven (27) tehsils, fifty nine (59) census towns and three hundred (300) villages.

Figure 18 Location map of delhi

Demographic trends

Demographic Trends Delhi ranks second in population among Indian cities according to the 2011 census wherein its population was recorded to be 16.7 million as against 13.9 million in 2001.

CHAPTER-3
DESKTOP - STUDY

Figure 19 Delhi population from 1901-2011

Traffic and Travel Characteristics

The Government of National Capital Territory of Delhi has been working towards a safe, sustainable, economic, people-friendly and efficient public transportation system in the city.

Presently transport demand of the city is met by public, intermediate public transport and personalised modes. These include intra-city buses, metro rail, inter-state bus services, suburban railways, auto rickshaws, cycle rickshaws, high capacity three wheelers (Gramin Sewa), hired cars and personalised modes such as cars and twowheelers. Buses and metro rail continue to be the most popular means of transportation for intra-city travel in the city.

Per Capita Trip Rate

Per capita trip rate including walk is estimated at 1.38, without walk it is 0.91 and for motorised trips it is 0.76.

Table 5 Rate per capita trip

Rate Per Capita Trip	
Including walk	1.38
Without walk	0.91
Motorized trips	0.76

Average Trip Length and Travel Time

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The average distance travelled by each mode varies; from 11.03 km by cars, 9.12 km by two wheelers, 10.23 km by buses and 12.66 km by metro rail. The average travel time is about 30 minutes by car, 26 minutes by two-wheelers, 32 minutes by buses, and 26 minutes by metro rail (Table 2-5). 10 Per capita trip rate and average trip length are the indicators of travel demand.

Traffic Congestion

A. Increase in personal vehicles: Increase in number of cars and two-wheelers is a major contributor to the congestion experienced in Delhi. The growth rate of the personal vehicles category is seen to be the highest. The pace of this increase has also been accelerating lately. This is worsening the air quality and congestion experienced in the city.

B. Registration of vehicles: It is galloping at an alarming pace. In 2011-12, Delhi registered over 471,000 private vehicles (both cars and two-wheelers) during the year. This figure jumped to over 939,000 personal vehicles during the year 2013- 14.

C. Roads overcrowded even when more than half of the population does not own motorised transport: In this populous city of 16.7 million, vehicles are overcrowding city roads even when over half of its population does not own any motorised vehicle. Just about 20 per cent of the households in Delhi own cars. Once two-wheelers are included, about 43 per cent of the households own motorised vehicles.

D. Multiple vehicles ownership: It is seen that amongst the vehicle owning households, more households are buying more than one vehicle.

E. Inter-city traffic: Not only are the vehicle numbers increasing in the city, influx of vehicles from outside the city is further adding to the traffic. For example, a key artery Nizamuddin bridge in Delhi takes the brunt of the incoming traffic from outside with nearly 80 per cent of the traffic in the morning peak hour is from outside the city. Similarly, in the evening peak hour, 75 per cent of vehicles at Income Tax Office (ITO) are from outside. This greatly burdens Delhi's roads and pollution load

F. Peak hour traffic has slowed considerably in Delhi: On an average, it is estimated that to provide a congestion free ride, the traffic speed should be close to 40 kmph. But studies carried out by various agencies in Delhi show that peak hour speed is much less as compared to this. A survey by RITES in 2008 shows that the peak hour speed is 22

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kmph hour and off-peak speed is about 26 kmph. This despite Delhi having about 46 flyovers, 33 ROBs, 17 RUBs and 7 river bridges and has nearly 20 per cent of its land is under roads/transport category usage. The RITES survey also shows that over 70 per cent of road length has peak hour traffic speed less than 30 kmph.

Travel Demand Forecast

From travel demand forecast it is observed that the mode share of public transport is projected to be 59% by 2021. Modal share of private vehicle (cars and two-wheelers) is projected to be 37% by year 2021. This indicates that the public transport provisioning will need to be augmented in order to cater to the projected public transport demand.

Volume to Capacity (V/C) ratio indicates the intensity of utilisation of road space. Accordance to the survey conducted by RITES for Government of NCT Delhi in 2007, V/C ratio varied between 0.3 and 2.83 on major roads. It is projected in the said survey that daily trips are going to increase by about 50% in 2021 as against the 2007 levels. This shows that there is a need for improvement in the infrastructure in order to provide for the projected volume of trips.

Proposed Multi Modal Transport Network for Delhi

The vision of Government of NCT of Delhi is to have an extensive and robust public transport system in place so that the share of trips catered to by public transport rises to 80%.

Revamping of the public transport infrastructure is already underway at present in the form of expansion of metro rail connectivity, augmentation of bus fleet, etc. Transport system of the city is being improved under an integrated multi-modal public transport plan to cater to the demand up to 2021. Metro, Light Rail and BRT systems have been recommended for various corridors based on estimated demand. In accordance with the public transport plan, total length of metro rail within Delhi and NCR by 2021 will be about 330 km; light rail about 40.3 km and BRT about 650 km.

Figure 20 Proposed multi modal public transport system

Existing Public Transport

The transport system of the capital city is indeed diverse, consisting of several modes. About 23 million passenger trips are made in the city every day, of which about 60 percent are catered to by Public and Intermediate Public Transport (IPT) including buses (operated by different operators), metro rail, taxis, auto rickshaws and nonmotorised modes such as cycle rickshaws. However, buses continue to be the most popular means of transportation for intra-city travel and cater to about 40% of the motorised trips. It continues to act as a major mode of transport, especially for the lower and middle income groups of the society.

Government of National Capital Territory of Delhi (GNCTD) has taken up several initiatives to boost the public transport infrastructure to keep pace with the ever growing demand through introduction of metro rail, development and improvement of transport nodes in the form of interstate bus terminals, multi-modal interchanges etc. Bus services are also being improved through fleet augmentation as well as by way of introduction of low floor buses, development of BRT corridors and introduction of intelligent transport systems for optimal routing, scheduling and passenger information dissemination.

Buses

Delhi has one of the largest bus transport systems in India. Buses are operated by the state-owned Delhi Transport Corporation (DTC), which owns the largest fleet of Compressed Natural Gas (CNG)-fuelled buses and by the Transport Department,

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Government of NCT of Delhi through the private bus operators as part of its Cluster bus scheme.

DTC is under the administrative control of the Transport Department, Government of NCT of Delhi. The fleet size of DTC as on June 2016 is 4,237 buses of which an average of 3,647 are scheduled for operation during a day.

Presently, there are 657 routes notified by the Transport Department. The length of the present bus route network of Delhi is about 16,200 km. The routes have been divided into 17 clusters based on their areas of operation. In 2011, the “Cluster Bus Scheme” has been launched in Delhi, wherein private operators have been selected to operate the bus services of various Clusters through bidding processes under the gross cost model. There are about 1500 buses operational under this scheme. These buses are fitted with intelligent transport systems such as Global Positioning System (GPS) devices and Passenger Information System (PIS) displays.

Metro Rail Network

The Delhi Metro Rail’s network consists of about 213 km of route length and 160 stations that are presently operational in Delhi and NCR. The urban mobility pattern has undergone a sea change with the gradual expansion of the metro and currently over 3 million passengers use the system every day.

The Government has approved the Phase-III of Delhi Metro and it is under an advance stage of construction having 13 corridors with route length of 160.57 km. The main motive behind the recommended corridors for Phase-III network has been to give metro network smooth connectivity by providing multiple interchange stations for switching from one corridor to another. This will reduce the travel time for metro commuters

Figure 21 Delhi metro network

Suburban Railway Network

The suburban railway is mostly used for inter-city travel in the Delhi NCR by about 0.61 million passenger per day (2007). It is also popular for movement of goods, vegetables, fishes, etc.

Figure 22 sub urban railway network

Transport Performance Indices

Transport Performance Indices were computed for Delhi as a part of the MoUD study¹⁸ for variables such as Public Transport, congestion, walkability, safety, parking and city bus supply.

Table 6 Transport performance indices

Index	Value
Public transport accessibility index	1.09
Congestion index	0.47
Walkability index	0.87
City bus transport supply index	44
Safety index	0.32
Para transit index	75.6
Slow moving vehicle index	0.04
On street parking interference index	2.82

Conclusion and Need Assessment

Based on the analysis of city characteristics, the following points emerge:

1. **Traffic Congestion:** The numbers of vehicles in Delhi are increasing at a rate higher than the road network expansion. This has created congestion on the Delhi's roads and accordingly the average speed of vehicles on the city roads has slowed down. National Urban Transport Helpline (NUTH) is intended to help individuals make more informed travel decisions, and thereby moderate the effects of traffic congestion on themselves as well as on other travellers. NUTH will provide traffic related information e.g. congestion on roads, alternate routes, construction and maintenance activity, incident activity information, etc. This information would help users take alternate route and save travel time. This will also lead to reducing pressure on congested routes and increased efficiency of system.
2. **Travel Demand:** Population, economic growth, number of registered motor vehicles and traffic levels all show an increasing trend in the city. These indicators clearly highlight the trend towards growing travel demand in the city due to the changing profile of the city. This supports the need to put in place information dissemination system like NUTH which can disseminate traveller information such as congestion on routes, details of transit routes, schedules, fares, expected time of arrival of transit, running status, multi-modal trip planning, etc.

3. **Modal Share:** It is projected that modal share of public transport in Delhi will be over 59% and that of private vehicles will be 37% by the year 2021. These figures represent the high use of both the public transportation and private vehicles. NUTH will cater to both, the users of public transport as well as private vehicles, as it will disseminate both transit and traffic information. Transit information will cover Estimated Time of Arrival (ETA), real time running status of transit, transit routes etc. This will help in increasing the reliability of public transport which will also lead to increase in use of public transport.
4. **Trip Rate:** The per capita trip rate for Delhi is increasing due to socio-economic factors, higher number of work trips, education trips and recreational trips. Higher trip rate would lead to increased demand for transport and consequent congestion on roads. NUTH will support in making travel more informed by providing traffic and transit information.
5. **Public Transport Accessibility Index** for Delhi is 1.09 which is lower than the desirable value of 2. Access to information about public transport like nearest bus stops, terminals, expected arrival time of public transport and running status on the map help in increasing accessibility to public transport. NUTH system would help increase the public transport accessibility by way of transit related information dissemination to public.
6. **Congestion index** of city is 0.47 which indicates that the average speed of network is lower by 50% than desired speed level. NUTH system would provide information like congestion level on GIS maps, alternate routes, construction and maintenance activities information, incident information, etc. Such information will help traveller in taking alternate routes that will result in saving of time by the traveller, besides reducing the burden on congested roads and also increasing the efficient utilisation of road network.
7. **Public Information Dissemination System:** The information regarding the schedules and routes of public transport services is mostly fragmented and scattered across various sources which not only inconveniences the transit users but also discourages modal shift from private to public transport modes. A few corridors in Delhi are provided with passenger information system. There is a need to have public information dissemination system for the commuters which can provide information regarding the public transport routes, traffic congestion on the roads, schedule of public transport systems etc. An effective public transport information dissemination system would enable potential users

to plan multi-modal journeys, minimise wait times at stations, and increase the overall satisfaction with the public transport and help in catalysing its adoption.

8. **Integration of Transport Modes:** There is a need to have an information dissemination system such as NUTH that would provide a unified view of all public transport modes to the public and help in planning multi-modal journeys.

Considering the presence of multiple modes and transit agencies in Delhi, there is clearly a need to establish NUTH system for Delhi to provide both multi-agency and multi-modal transit information, as well as traffic related information to public. It should provide static and real time information related to transit as well as traffic

Need for NUTH and some of the benefits of the proposed NUTH for Delhi are provided below:

- **Unified System for Urban Transport Information System:** Delhi NUTH would be a unified system that would be accessible to public through multiple channels for providing all urban transport related information including the traffic, transit and parking related information.
- **Traffic Information Dissemination:** Currently traffic information is provided by Delhi Traffic Police through their website, social media pages, helpline and mobile app. Delhi NUTH would be accessible to public through multiple channels for providing the traffic related information as a single unified source.
- **Transit Information Dissemination:** Currently transit information is provided by individual transit agencies for their respective modes. Delhi NUTH would be a common platform that would provide transit related information for all the transit operators to public through multiple channels.
- **Parking Information Dissemination:** Currently parking information is provided by individual parking agencies for their respective sites in a limited way. Delhi NUTH would be accessible to public through multiple channels for providing the parking related information for various parking agencies.
- **Incident/ Construction and Maintenance Information Dissemination:** Currently incident related information is provided by Delhi Traffic Police through their website, social media pages, helpline and mobile apps. The information related to

construction/ maintenance is generally not available. Delhi NUTH would be accessible to public through multiple channels for providing the incident/ construction and maintenance related information as a single unified source.

- **Multi-Modal Information Dissemination System:** Presently various transit agencies disseminate transit information through their respective channels for their respective modes (e.g. DTC, DMRC, DIMTS for Cluster Buses etc.) only. Information regarding the schedules and routes of public transport services in Delhi is mostly fragmented and scattered across various sources which not only inconveniences the transit users but also discourages modal shift from private to public transport modes. NUTH would act as a unified system from where users/ general public can get information about various transportation modes in the city.
- **Reducing Traffic Congestion:** Delhi NUTH would help individuals make more informed travel decisions thereby support in moderating the effects of traffic congestion on the road network. NUTH will provide information e.g. congestion on roads, alternate routes, construction and maintenance activity, incident information etc. This information would help users in taking alternate routes preventing not just congestion from aggravating but would also support in efficient utilisation of transport infrastructure.
- **Improvement in Public Transport Modal Share:** NUTH will inter alia disseminate transit and traffic information. Transit information will cover routes and schedules information for various transit modes, Estimated Time of Arrival (ETA), real time running status, and routes on which particular transit is available among others. This would help in increasing the reliability of public transport and would support in attracting public to shift to public transport leading to its enhanced share in overall transport trips.

NUTH Implementation process:

- NUTH implementation process for the system would broadly include Concept Development phase (2-3 months); Systems Engineering Management Plan (2-4 months); Detailed Design, Detailed Project Report and Detailed Agreement between Stakeholders (2-4 months); Preparation of Tender Document (2 months);

Bid Process Management (3 months); and Project Implementation, Monitoring and Management (6-9 months). A total of 17-25 months period is projected for project planning, procurement and implementation

Figure 23 NUTH Implementation process

Project cost

The costs have been worked out based on costs of similar international and Indian deployments and are indicative in nature. The costs must be refined and finalised during the DPR stage and as part of systems engineering and design phases of the project.

NUTH Sizing

Sizing of NUTH will depend upon the following factors:

- Amount of information to be collected and processed by NUTH

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- Number of servers, leased communication line, computer hardware etc. required to handle information collection and dissemination
- Number of personnel deployed
- Volume/duration of session seeking information request.

A budget of ₹ 16.04 crores is required for Phase 1 implementation of Delhi NUTH project, which include the projects development, systems engineering, hardware, software, systems integration, testing, commissioning. In addition, a budget of ₹ 5.65 crores is required towards annual operations and maintenance of the NUTH.

Table 7 Budget for NUTH

Description	Implementation cost	O &M costs
NUTH	16,04,51,800	5,65,45,000

Revenue Streams

Delhi NUTH project may not be able to generate any revenue by charging users. Worldwide also such services are provided by government entities free of cost to the users with users having to bear the cost of making calls to the transport helpline numbers providing information generated by the NUTH. The data being collected may be shared by Delhi NUTH with various entities (including the private sector) without any charges to begin with, but with an option to charge for the same retained by the implementing agency.

Some of the funding sources that could be used and/or allocated for operating and maintaining the Delhi NUTH are as under:

- Fines collected through the enforcement measures
- Parking charges collected from users
- Receipts from private entities for sharing data
- Receipts from advertisers against grant of right to display advertisements on website, mobile, helpline apps providing information generated by NUTH
- Receipts from sponsorship by corporates in lieu of exclusive right to co-brand

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One of the pre-requisites to the possibility of realisation of revenue from data is the utility, popularity and marketability of the data. Similarly, number of users accessing any particular channel (website, mobile app, helpline) would determine its appeal to advertisers. Content quality, brand perception and popularity of service would, therefore, be the key determinants of revenue realisation potential from data marketing/ information dissemination activities.

It may be noted that the quantum of funding available from the fines collected by the Traffic Police through enforcement measures may go down progressively as the compliance to the traffic rules improves which, in any case, is the end objective of implementing the enforcement measures.

Figure 24 Best practices

CHAPTER-4
SITE AREA

Introduction to the site

- The Hyderabad Metropolitan Development Authority (HMDA) was formed by an Act (G.O.Ms.No.570 MA & UD (I1) Dept., dt.25.08.2008) in the year 2008, with an area of 7,257 Sq. Km
- HMDA jurisdiction covers (7) Districts, (70) Mandals, 1032 Villages including Greater Hyderabad Municipal Corporation consisting of 175 Villages and 40 Municipalities / Nagar Panchayats consisting of 138 villages and remaining 719 Villages under jurisdiction of the HMDA. Go's Alloted for each of the jurisdictions.

- Districts involved in jurisdiction
- Hyderabad
 - Part of Rangareddy
 - Part of Medak
 - Part of Siddipet
 - Part of Yadadri
 - Part of Vikarabad
 - Part of Sangareddy

Figure 25 Jurisdictions of HMDA

Transportation scenario in HMDA

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No	System	Units	Upto 2011	2021-31
1	Total Road network	Km	5,400	
2	Metro Rail System	Km	162	328
3	Bus Rapid Transit System	Km	57	153
4	Multi Modal Transit System	Km	193**	355
5	Highway System	Lane-Km	22600***	13200
6	Passenger Terminals (Rail, Road)	No	2,9	1,16
7	Bridges, Flyovers, RoB/RuBs	No	12,47,25	0,0,24

Bus transportation:

TSRTC is the responsible agency for operating buses in HMDA

Formation : 2nd june 2014 [After bifurcation of Andhra Pradesh

Ridership : 33.04 lakhs per day

History:

Road transport corporation in Telangana State was first established as NSRRTD (Nizam State Rail & Road Transport Department), a wing of Nizam State Railway in the erstwhile Hyderabad State, in 1932, with 27 buses and 166 employees. Andhra Pradesh State Road Transport Corporation (APSRTC) was established on 11 January 1958 in pursuance of the Road Transport Corporations Act 1950. Consequent upon bifurcation of Andhra Pradesh state into Telangana and residual Andhra Pradesh, TSRTC operated as a separate entity from 03.06.2015.

The Government of Telangana has subsequently established Telangana State Road Transport Corporation (TSRTC), on 27.03.2016, under the Road Transport Corporation Act, 1950.

Divisions: TSRTC has three zones: Hyderabad Rural (HR), Greater Hyderabad (GHZ), and Karimnagar (KRMR). It is further subdivided into 13 regions and 24 divisions.460 buses, of which around 2000 are hired vehicles.

Table 1 List of Depots & Number of Buses Operated from each Depot

S.No.	Depot name	Depot code	No.of buses
1	BHEL	BHEL	125
2	Barkathpura	BKP	132
3	Contonment	CNT	182
4	Dilsukhnagar	DSNR	175
5	Falaknuma	FM	162
6	HCU	HCU	131

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7	Hakimpet	HPT	156
8	Hayathnagar-1	HYT-1	155
9	Hayathnagar-2	HYT-2	114
10	Ibrahimpattanam	IBP	139
11	Jeedimetla	JDM	172
12	Kacheguda	KG	191
13	Kukatpally	KP	155
14	Medchal	MDCL	125
15	Midhani	MDN	147
16	Mehdipattanam	MP	190
17	Musheerabad-1	MSRD-1	106
18	Musheerabad-2	MSRD-2	127
19	Miyapur-1	MYP-1	134
20	Miyapur-2	MYP-2	134
21	Rajendranagar	RJNR	166
22	Ranigunj-1	RNG-1	160
23	Ranigunj-2	RNG-2	168
24	Uppal	UPL	208
Total			3645

A total number of 776 bus routes are playing on the road for public transport (other than hired/ company/ institution Buses) with 1706 bus stops. The total trips performed by these 776 routes per day are about 44,000. TSRTC

Ticketing and fares:

Minimum bus charges	
Pallevelugu Buses:	Rs. 10/-
Deluxe Buses:	Rs.20/-
Express Buses:	Rs.15/-
Super Luxury Buses:	Rs.25/-
Rajadhani, Vajra, Garuda, Garuda Plus Buses:	Rs.35/-
Vennela AC Sleeper Buses:	Rs.75/-
Bus pass fares	
City Ordinary Bus pass Charge:	Rs. 950
Metro Bus Pass Charge:	Rs. 1070
Metro Deluxe Bus Pass Charge:	Rs. 1180
Student Bus Pass Charge:	Rs. 495

Figure 26 Bus routes in HMDA region

MMTS:

The Hyderabad Multi-Modal Transport System, commonly abbreviated MMTS, is a suburban rail system in Hyderabad, India. A joint venture of the government of Telangana and the South Central Railway

History

The first phase was opened to the public on 9 August 2003 by Deputy Prime Minister of India L.K. Advani.[2] The second phase was opened by N.Chandrababu Naidu, chief minister of Andhra Pradesh.[3][4] The system has three lines, with total length of 44 kilometres (27 mi). In May, 2010, Indian Railways decided to take over the 107-kilometre (66 mi) Phase II project at an estimated cost of ₹ 641 crore. The Railway Board cleared the second phase after the state government agreed to fund two-thirds of the cost, and it is under construction.

Routes

A total of 9 MMTS routes are operating in HMA area. Summary of MMTS routes operated by SCR in HMA are presented in Table.

S.No	Direction	No.of stops	Route length in km.	Scheduled trains/day
1	Falaknuma to lingampally	22	38	28
2	Lingampally to Falaknuma	22	38	30
3	Hyderabad to lingampally	13	24	26
4	Lingampally to Hyderabad	13	24	23
5	Falaknuma to hyderabad	17	24	5
6	Hyderabad to Falaknuma	17	24	3
7	Falaknuma to Secundrabad	11	15	2
8	Secundrabad to Falaknuma	11	15	2
9	Lingampally to Secundrabad	12	23	1
	Total			121

Figure 27 MMTS routes in HMDA region

Ticketing and fares

MMTS Train General class Fares

- 0-05 km -Rs.5/-
- 06-10 km -Rs.5/-
- 11-15 km -Rs.5/-
- 16-20 km -Rs.5/-
- 21-25 km -Rs.10/-
- 26-30 km -Rs.10/-
- 31-35 km -Rs.10/-
- 36-40 km -Rs.10/-

MMTS Train First class Fares

- 0-05 km -Rs.50/-
- 06-10 km -Rs.50/-

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11-15 km -Rs.65/-

16-20 km -Rs.95/-

21-25 km -Rs.100/-

26-30 km -Rs.145/-

31-35 km -Rs.145/-

36-40 km -Rs.155/-

MMTS Train General class Monthly Season Ticket Fares

0-05 km -Rs.150/-

06-10 km -Rs.150/-

11-15 km -Rs.150/-

16-20 km -Rs.150/-

21-25 km -Rs.280/-

26-30 km -Rs.280/-

31-35 km -Rs.280/-

36-40 km -Rs.280/-

MMTS Train First class Monthly Season Ticket Fares

0-05 km -Rs.510/-

06-10 km -Rs.510/-

11-15 km -Rs.635/-

16-20 km -Rs.750/-

21-25 km -Rs.885/-

26-30 km -Rs.900/-

31-35 km -Rs.1025/-

36-40 km -Rs.1135/-

MMTS-um-General Bus Ticket(GBT) Fare is Rs. 800/- per Month

Hyderabad metro rail [HMRL]:

Hyderabad Metro Rail (HMR) is the world's largest Public-Private Partnership (PPP) project in the Metro rail sector. Metro rail and other forms of Mass Rapid Transport System (MRTS) are emerging as prominent infrastructure requirement offering a viable solution to the transportation woes that accompany urban expansion. Hyderabad Metro Rail (HMR) Project is an integrated urban transport development project with inter-modal connectivity and convenient sky walks that will mark the beginning of an era of seamless commuting across Hyderabad. was inaugurated on 28 November 2017 by Prime Minister Narendra Modi. [

History

Metro Rail Project was approved by Union government, in 2003.[24] As Hyderabad continued to grow, the Multi-Modal Transport System (MMTS) had insufficient capacity for public transport, and the Union Ministry of Urban Development approved construction of the Hyderabad Metro Rail Project, directing the Delhi Metro Rail Corporation to conduct a survey of the proposed lines and to submit a Detailed Project Report (DPR).[25] To meet rising public transport needs and mitigate growing road traffic in the twin cities of Hyderabad and Secunderabad, the state government and the South Central Railway jointly launched the MMTS in August 2003.[26][27] The initial plan was for the Metro to connect with the existing MMTS to provide commuters with alternate modes of transport. Simultaneously, the proposals for taking up the construction of MMTS Phase II were also taken forward.[28]

Network

The Hyderabad Metro Rail Network will cover a total distance of around 69.2 Km across three corridors:

- Corridor I : Miyapur to LB Nagar- – 29 km; 27 Stations
- Corridor II : JBS to MGBS- 28 km; 23 Stations
- Corridor III : Nagole to Raidurgam- 15 km (11 km); 15 (10) Stations

Total stations 64 – 3 interchanges

Ticketing and Fare

Table 9 Ticketing and fares for HMRL

S.No	Distance	Ticket Fare
1	0 to 2 Kms	Rs.10
2	2 to 4 Kms	Rs.15
3	4 to 6 Kms	Rs.25
4	6 to 8 Kms	Rs.30
5	8 to 10 Kms	Rs.35
6	10 to 14 Kms	Rs.40
7	14 to 18 Kms	Rs.45
8	18 to 22 Kms	Rs.50
9	22 to 26 Kms	Rs.55
10	More than 26 Kms	Rs.60

Figure 28 HMRL routes and stations

Objective -1: Studying existing scenario

1.1 Assessment of Vehicular emissions

Hyderabad is one of the fastest growing centers of urban development in India. This growth has also brought with it air quality and congestion problems. For a number of reasons, motorized two wheelers, auto rickshaws and private passenger cars, have displaced trip making which has been more traditionally accomplished by public transport and bicycle.

Traffic congestion, the predominance of two-stroke vehicles in the traffic mix and inability of public (bus) transport to attract significant ridership have all been blamed for the severe air quality problems in Hyderabad especially the prevalence of Respirable Particulate Matter (PM10) as well as rapidly growing emissions of Greenhouse Gases (GHGs).

RITES has identified 3 more corridors in addition to the GEP Corridor (ESI Hospital to Khairatabad Junction, Length=4.6km) as a part of the study component on “Traffic Management & Measures to Improve Traffic Flow” The corridors are:

- (i) Erragadda junction to ESI Hospital (NH-9), L=0.9km
- (ii) Khairatabad junction to Nalgonda ‘X’ roads (NH-9) via Nampelly Public Garden and MJ Market, L=7.1km
- (iii) Panjagutta junction to Secunderabad Retifile bus station via Green lands and Begumpet road, L=8.05km

Estimation of vehicular emissions

The IVE (International Vehicle Emissions) Model developed jointly by University of California, Riverside, College of Engineering – center for Environmental Research and Technology (CE-CERT), Global Sustainable Systems Research (GSSR) and the International Sustainable Systems Research Center (ISSRC) has been used for estimation of emissions for BAU and policy options scenarios. The input data for running IVE model are mode wise vehicle kilometers traveled, vehicle startups, average speeds, altitude, humidity, temperature, mode wise driving style distribution, soak time distribution, fuel characteristics, etc. Mode wise driving style distribution,

soak time distributions and mode wise vehicle technology distribution were taken to be the same as the Pune Vehicle Activity Study (India) carried out by CECERT.

IVE model was then run for BAU, More Effective Public Transit scenario and Traffic Management and Measures to Improve Traffic Flow scenarios as discussed above to estimate the vehicular emissions for the years 2003, 2011 & 2021.

For vehicle/technology training measures, overall reduction in emissions has been worked at assuming a certain level of reduction in existing in 2-stroke vehicles and their penetration rates for the years 2011 and 2021.

Vehicular emissions survey

The vehicular emissions monitoring was carried out in following locations (5 Junctions & 6 Mid Blocks) during typical working day continuously from 6 am to next day 6 am (24 hours) along with atmospheric temperature and wind speed measurements. In mid blocks sections, survey was carried out at one side/median of the road depending upon the site conditions

Sampling Locations along with the Sampling Date		
Station Code	Sampling Location	Sampling Date
A	Ravindra Bharathi Junction	03.03.03-04.03.2003
B	Ameerpet Junction	03.03.03-04.03.2003
C	Rajeev Gandhi Junction	04.03.03-05.03.2003
D	NTR/Rasoolpura Junction	04.03.03-05.03.2003
E	Sangeet Theatre Junction	05.03.03-06.03.2003
F	Nalgonda X Roads Junction	05.03.03-06.03.2003
G	Mid point of Hari Hara Kala Bhavan and Parade Ground Fly Over	06.03.03-07.03.2003
H	Chaderghat (Mid point)	06.03.03-07.03.2003
I	Erragada near Gokul Theatre (Mid point)	07.03.03-08.03.2003
J	Panjagutta near NIMS Hospital (Mid point)	07.03.03-08.03.2003
K	MJ Market near Care Hospital (Mid point)	07.03.03-08.03.2003

Figure 29 Sampling locations

Air Quality Exposure Index (AQEI)

For assessing the ambient air quality (AAQ) status, Air Quality Exposure Index (AQEI) concept has been used. Among the various air quality indices, Oak Ridge-Air Quality Index (ORAQI) is found most useful in depicting ambient air quality parameters (SPM, SO₂ and NO_x) into a single value, as it clearly defines the AAQ status and also meets the criteria of uniform AQI, suggested by Thom and Off (1975).

ORAQI is calculated using the equation: $ORAQI = (a \sum C_i/S_i)^b$

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Where a and b are constants, Ci is monitored/predicted concentration of pollutant 'i' and S is National Air Quality Standard for pollutant i.

Air Quality Exposure Index (AQEI) and Air Quality Categories in the Study Area

Station Code	Sampling Station	24 hourly Avg. Conc. (µg/m³)			AQEI	Category
		TSPM	SO ₂	NO _x		
A	Ravindra Bharati Junction	295	27	67	103	Dangerous
B	Ameerpet Junction	201	28	129	112	Dangerous
C	Rajeev Gandhi Junction	346	27	54	104	Dangerous
D	NTR/Rasoolpura Junction	268	22	64	91	Bad
E	Sangeet Theatre Junction	499	20	47	125	Dangerous

Station Code	Sampling Station	24 hourly Avg. Conc. (µg/m³)			AQEI	Category
		TSPM	SO ₂	NO _x		
F	Nalgonda X Roads	451	25	66	127	Dangerous
G	Harihara Kala Bhavan	253	21	52	83	Bad
H	Chaderghat RUB	431	37	89	139	Dangerous
I	Erragadda Junction	332	35	75	101	Dangerous
J	Punjagutta Junction	675	30	51	159	Dangerous
K	MJ Market Junction	227	16	32	66	Poor

Figure 30 AQEI values for samples

Figure 31 Air quality monitoring stations

Estimated Daily emissions

Estimated Daily Emissions For Study Area: BAU

Y E A R	VKT/day	EMISSIONS IN METRIC TONNES PER DAY						
		CO	NOX	SOX	PM	CO ₂	N ₂ O	CH ₄
2001	16851248	503.27	27.72	0.40	5.00	2314.71	0.02	24.15
2003	21293038	630.15	34.22	0.50	6.27	2916.00	0.03	30.41
2011	33674458	1206.65	58.58	0.9	12.18	5144.47	0.04	61.21
2021	51260905	3044.78	128.17	2.08	32.54	11237.75	0.1	171.31

Figure 32 estimated daily emissions

Daily estimations with more effective Bus transit scenario:

Ability of public transportation in reduction of pollutant emissions could assessed from this study

Daily Emissions With More Effective Bus Transit Scenario: Entire Study Area

S. No	YEAR	VKT/day	POLLUTION LOAD IN METRIC TONNES PER DAY						
			CO	NO _x	SO _x	PM	CO ₂	N ₂ O	CH ₄
1	2011	26244325	879.45	49.87	0.75	7.92	4456.37	0.04	37.66
2	2021	36189703	1634.38	91.42	1.26	14.58	7445.06	0.07	69.56

Reduction In Emissions For Various Scenarios

Reduction Due To More Effective Bus Transit Scenario In Entire Study Area (In Tonnes)

YEAR	CO	NO _x	SO _x	PM	CO ₂	N ₂ O	CH ₄
2011	327.20 (27)	8.71 (15)	0.15 (17)	4.26 (35)	688.05 (13)	0.00 (0)	23.55 (38)
2021	1410.40 (46)	36.75 (29)	0.82 (39)	17.96 (55)	3792.69 (34)	0.03 (30)	101.75 (59)

Figure 33 Daily emissions with effective bus transit

1.2 Understanding trip generations and Modal splits

Travel demand models are employed in decision making process of large infrastructure related projects by simulating the effects of key governing variables to appropriate levels of accuracy. For facilitating the decision making process, travel demand models are calibrated for the base year situation and then utilised for forecasting travel patterns and the evaluation of various supply measures with economic and environmental perspectives for the horizon years.

Table 8-2: Purpose and Mode wise Daily Travel Demand from Demadj Process

Purpose	Train	Bus	Car	Two-Wheeler	Auto Rickshaw	Taxi	NMT	Total
Home Based Work	54,035	526,844	116,303	1,115,705	160,714	59,093	1,056,162	3,088,855
Home Based Education	15,701	704,100	13,736	167,204	72,236	13,055	931,870	1,917,902
Home Based Others	32,013	181,988	145,638	316,475	121,295	22,792	214,432	1,034,634
Non Home Based	1,223	146,881	53,731	248,933	64,282	20,661	11,484	547,196
Return Home Work	62,395	728,416	104,945	1,018,191	154,525	62,943	1,079,126	3,210,542
Return Home Education	16,109	662,568	8,921	140,452	53,596	9,641	893,086	1,784,373
Return Home Others	21,614	142,419	126,898	113,768	63,447	17,876	213,687	699,710
Total	203,090	3,093,218	570,172	3,120,729	690,095	206,061	4,399,847	12,283,212

Table 8-18: Revalidation of Mode Choice Models: Weighted Coincidence Ratio

Purpose	Train	Bus	Car	Two-Wheeler	Auto Rickshaw	Taxi	Weighted CR
HBW	2.4%	26.1%	5.2%	53.9%	7.2%	5.2%	0.80423
HBE	1.7%	67.6%	1.5%	17.7%	7.7%	3.8%	0.77702
HBO	3.7%	21.7%	16.3%	39.6%	13.9%	4.8%	0.63785
NHB	0.2%	26.0%	9.5%	45.8%	11.7%	6.7%	0.61905
RHW	2.7%	32.2%	5.2%	47.8%	7.0%	5.1%	0.78745
RHE	1.7%	71.4%	1.0%	15.5%	6.4%	4.0%	0.77046
RHO	4.5%	29.9%	25.0%	23.1%	12.2%	5.4%	0.57188

Figure 34 Existing purpose and modal choices

Figure 8-5: Assigned Rail and Bus Passenger Flows for Morning Peak Period (Base Year 2011)

Figure 8-6: Assigned Road PCU Flows for Morning Peak Period (Base Year 2011)

Figure 35 Assigned rail and bus passenger flows for morning peak period (2011)

Figure 36 Assigned road PCU flows for morning peak period (2011)

Transport network analysis by scenarios

Permutations and combinations of three land use scenarios, two network scenarios and two private vehicle growth scenarios results in twelve alternative scenarios for travel demand and network analysis for the horizon year 2041. Variations in population and employment distributions in three land use scenarios (S1, S3 and S4), variations in private vehicle growth assumptions (demand side factors) and response of the two alternative transport networks i.e. N2 and N3 (supply side factors) results in varied mode choices and travel patterns in alternative scenarios.

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Figure 8-19: Alternative Scenarios for Travel Demand Analysis

Figure 37 Alternative scenarios for travel demand analysis

Table 8-41: Comparative Evaluation of Growth Scenarios

Scenario	Cost of Transport Network	Pass-km by Bus, Suburban & Metro	Average Speed of Bus, Suburban & Metro	Trip Length of Bus, Suburban & Metro	Average Speed of PV, IPT and Goods Modes	Weighted Rank	Overall Ranking
Weights	25%	25%	10%	15%	25%		100%
S1N2PV1	6	4	10	9	7	7	7
S1N2PV2	4	11	12	6	11	8	12
S3N2PV1	1	5	9	6	13	7	6
S3N2PV2	2	10	11	5	9	7	10
S4N2PV1	5	6	7	2	12	7	9
S4N2PV2	3	12	8	1	8	7	8
S1N3PV1	7	1	4	11	10	7	5
S1N3PV2	12	6	6	10	3	7	11
S3N3PV1	8	2	2	10	6	6	2
S3N3PV2	10	8	5	8	2	7	4
S4N3PV1	11	3	1	7	5	6	3
S4N3PV2	9	9	3	3	1	6	1

Figure 38 Comparative evaluation of growth scenarios

S4N3PV2 scenario

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Population	Employment	Mode split	System cost (INR crores)
Inside ORR :14.5 m	Inside ORR : 5.4m	Public transportation :25.3%	Transit: 28,724(57%)
ORR and Outside: 4.8m	RoR and Outside :2.3m	IPT:1.7%, private:73.0%	Roads: 38,712 (43%)

Figure 39 S4N3PV2 scenarios

Objective-2 Understanding Coverage

2.1 Existing Public transit stations

Locations of existing transit stations with respect to modes of transportation Bus, Metro and MMTS

Figure 40 Base map [existing public transit stations

2.2 Coverage analysis

Aspects to cover under coverage analysis

1. Areas under Public transit station service
 2. Access with respect to minimum walking distance
1. Coverage analysis for areas under service of a public transit station can be assessed with Euclidean tools in order to understand 3 main aspects to know coverage which is as follow:

Figure 41 Euclidean tools

The Euclidean distance algorithm

Euclidean distance is calculated from the center of the source cell to the center of each of the surrounding cells. True Euclidean distance is calculated in each of the distance tools.

Conceptually, the Euclidean algorithm works as follows: for each cell, the distance to each source cell is determined by calculating the hypotenuse with x_max and y_max as the other two legs of the triangle. This calculation derives the true Euclidean distance, rather than the cell distance.

The shortest distance to a source is determined, and if it is less than the specified maximum distance, the value is assigned to the cell location on the output raster.

Figure 42 Euclidean algorithm

The output values for the Euclidean distance raster are floating-point distance values. If the cell is at an equal distance to two or more sources, the cell is assigned to the source that is first encountered in the scanning process. You cannot control this scanning process.

The above description is only a conceptual depiction of how values are derived. The actual algorithm computes the information using a two-scan sequential process. This process makes the speed of the tool independent from the number of source cells, the distribution of the source cells, and the maximum distance specified. The only factor that influences the speed with which the tool executes is the size of the raster. The computation time is linearly proportional to the number of cells in the Analysis window

Procedure:

Step-1: Open Arc Map arrange the layers required [Public transit stations, HMDA Boundary, Road network]

Step-2: Open Tool boxes

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- Spatial Analyst tools
- Distance
- Euclidean Distance , Euclidean Direction, Euclidean Allocation
- Insert input as transit stations
- Click on environments
- Set processing extent as HMDA layer
- Click OK

The Euclidean distance output raster

The Euclidean distance output raster contains the measured distance from every cell to the nearest source. The distances are measured as the crow flies (Euclidean distance) in the projection units of the raster, such as feet or meters, and are computed from cell center to cell center.

Figure 1 Euclidean distance

The Euclidean direction output raster

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The Euclidean direction output raster contains the azimuth direction from each cell to the nearest source. Euclidean direction assigns the direction of each cell in degrees to its nearest source. A 360-degree circle or compass is used, with 360 being to the north and 1 to the east; the remaining values increase clockwise.

The Euclidean allocation output raster

Every cell in the Euclidean allocation output raster is assigned the value of the source to which it is closest, as determined by the Euclidean distance algorithm.

Each cell in an allocation receives the value of the zone to which it will be allocated. A source is any cell or set of cells with the same value or belonging to the same zone. If a zone is disconnected, the value assigned to the cells allocated to that zone is the distance of the closest region of the zone.

The values for all non-source cells on the output raster will contain the same values assigned to the cells in the source raster or the values associated with each source location derived from the value raster.

Figure 2 Euclidean direction and allocation

Output:

- Zones with major area dependent on one public transit station

Figure 3 Output from euclidean tools

2. Access to public transit stations with respect to minimum walking distance

According to Sustainable development goal 11 of making cities and human settlements inclusive, safe, resilient and sustainable. The minimum walking distance by a human is 500m

Figure 4 Sustainable development goal 11

Figure 5 Buffer zones with 500m radius

Output:

Major Inaccessibility with respect to efficient walking distance

Objective-3 Understanding Efficiency

Aspects to cover under efficiency analysis

1. Efficiency levels with respect to modes of transportation
2. Spatial links of efficiency

Understanding performance is closely related with efficiency of functioning of the system in this approach at a national level this efficiency is measured with respect to standards

Strategy For better Public transportation: A case of Hyderabad Metropolitan Development area and process of a city or a system to undergo with the aspects of standards is called service level benchmarking

Service level benchmarks: Benchmarking is the process of measuring the performances of various elements of urban transport against a set standard or target. It provides policymakers with tools to continuously seek enhanced performance for their urban transport.

Figure 48 Indicators outlined by MOUD

The public transport facilities are measured by:

1. Presence of Organized Public Transport System in Urban Area (%)
2. Extent of Supply - Availability of Public Transport
3. Service Coverage of Public Transport in the city
4. Average waiting time for Public Transport users (min)
5. Level of Comfort in Public Transport (Crowding)
6. % fleet size as per urban bus specification

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1. Public Transport facilities

Level of Service	1. Presence of Organized Public Transport System in Urban Area (%)	2. Extent of Supply Availability of Public Transport	3. Service Coverage of Public Transport in the city	4. Average waiting time for Public Transport users (mins)	5. Level of Comfort in Public Transport	6. % of Fleet as per Urban Bus Specification
1	>= 60	>= 0.6	>= 1	<=4	<= 1.5	75 - 100
2	40- 60	0.4 - 0.6	0.7- 1	4 – 6	1.5 – 2.0	50 - 75
3	20 - 40	0.2 - 0.4	0.3 - 0.7	6 – 10	2.0 – 2.5	25 - 50
4	< 20	< 0.2	< 0.3	> 10	>2.5	<= 25
Overall Level of Service of Public Transport facilities City wide						
Calculated LoS = (LoS ₁ + LoS ₂ + LoS ₃ + LoS ₄ + LoS ₅ + LoS ₆) and identify overall LoS as mentioned below						
Overall LoS	Calculated LoS	Comments				
1	< 12	The City has a good public transport system which is wide spread and easily available to the citizens. The system provided is comfortable.				
2	12 - 16	The City has public transport system which may need considerable improvements in terms of supply of buses/ coaches and coverage as many parts of the city are not served by it. The frequency of the services available may need improvements. The system provided is comfortable.				
3	17 - 20	The City has a public transport system which may need considerable improvements in terms of supply of buses / coaches and coverage as most parts of the city are not served by it. The frequency of the services available needs improvements. The system provided is not comfortable as there is considerable over loading.				
4	21-24	The city has very poor/no organized public transport system				

Figure 49 Procedure of LOS calculation

Service level benchmarks for HMDA region:

Table 10 Service level benchmarks

Sl.no.	Service level benchmark	LoS	Remarks
1	Public transport facilities	2	The city has public transport system which may need considerable improvements in terms of supply of buses/ coaches and coverage as many parts of the city are not served by it. The frequencies of the services available need improvements. The system provided is comfortable but not adequate
2	Pedestrian infrastructure facilities	2	The city has pedestrian facilities which may need some improvements in terms of controls at intersections, on footpaths, and street lightings. Some parts of the city are not provided with footpaths / sidewalks. The footpath available need improvements to have better comforts. Many of the major roads have large commercial establishments located adjacent to them. This generate heavy pedestrian volumes and they are not adequately provided with facilities.
3	Non-motorized transport facilities	3	The city has NMT facilities which may need considerable improvements as many parts of the city are not served by it
4	Level of usage of Intelligent transport system	4	The city lacks adequate ITS facilities. At present surveillance cameras are used at 54 intersections to observe the traffic operations. Communication to the field staff of Traffic Police needs to be introduced.

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5	Travel speed (motorized and mass transit) along major corridors	2	Travel speeds are low for the reasons like absence of defined functions of the major roads and mixed nature of traffic. Roadside developments interfere with the traffic operations
6	Availability of parking spaces	2	Paid parking spaces are available in the city and the demand is well managed by incorporating differential parking rates for the CBD. However substantial improvements are required to meet the growing needs
7	Road safety	4	Fatality rate is very high more traffic controls devices are required to be installed and monitored
8	Pollution levels	1	Level of pollution in a city is reported to be within prescribed limits
9	Integrated land use transport system	4	Inconsistency in the city structure and public transport system leading to lesser ridership and high dependence on personalized motor vehicles
10	Financial sustainability of public transport	2	The public transport of a city is financially sustainable Improvements are required to better manage the staff

Source : Long term strategy by HMDA

1. Efficiency analysis with respect to modes of transportation

Requirement of an analysis technique where the efficiency is to be measured based on certain parameters [Responsible for shift to private vehicles from public]

3.1 Efficiency Scores from DEA Analysis

The DEA is a non-parametric method applied to compare the efficiency measurement of several units with the same objectives using linear programming. It gives an image of a general measure performance of different units

A key advantage of DEA was by handled multiple inputs and outputs; this gives comprehensive consideration for analysis units. Inputs and outputs of units depend on the properties of the system analyzed. Inputs represent resources to run the service, and the output represents the quality of service provided. Decision-making units (DMUs) are units evaluated by DEA, they are a collection of divisions or any other systems, and for example, it may be hospitals, banks, or transit systems. DEA is used to estimate weights in an objective and economical manner based on linear programming

A few features of DEA are:

- It avoids subjective evaluation; in the beginning, it does not need any weight.
- It does not require default input and output function.
- It suggests the change could occur to increase performance improvement

DEA is a linear programming problem as formulated in the equation below to determine the efficiency score E_k for each DMU_k

$$Max. E_k = \frac{\sum_{j=1}^n U_j^k y_j^k}{\sum_{i=1}^m V_i^k x_i^k} \dots\dots\dots(1)$$

$$Max. E_k = \frac{\sum_{j=1}^n U_j^k y_j^k}{\sum_{i=1}^m V_i^k x_i^k} \leq 1, \text{ the DMU is one of } R, r=1,2,\dots, R$$

$$1 \leq k \leq R$$

$$U_j^k \geq \varepsilon > 0, j = 1,2,3,4$$

$$V_i^k \geq \varepsilon > 0, i = 1$$

Where

u_j^k is a variable that represented the output j weight under the aim of maximizing efficiency

v_i^k is a decision variable that represented the input i weight under the aim of maximizing efficiency And ε is a non-archimedean number. (Q.Waheed, 2020)

In this case,

- Inputs are the factors which are directly responsible for shift to private from public major aspects in this perspective is comfort and time 4 parameters are been formulated as shown in table
- Decision making units are the aspects with respect to the modes of transport that are been included in my study.
- Output is linked with the overall performance of the system which is LOS of the public transport system in HMDA region.
- Overall Output : the overall output approach is efficiency scores of modes of transportation with respect to the parameters involved in direct shift to private

from public. This analysis of developing efficiency scores with the scenario of existing level of service LOS of the region as an output

Table 11 DEA analysis

Inputs	DMU	Output
Service reliability	Bus	Level of service [LOS] =2
Passenger load rate	Metro	
Average dwell time	MMTS	
Average running speed		

Step wise analysis

Step1: Formulation of data requirements

Table 12 Data requirements

Parameters	Time period	Bus	Average	Metro	Average	MMTS	Average
Passenger load	Peak (seating + standing)	120	90	1000	563	5,150	3075
	Off-Peak (seating)	60		126		1000	
Service reliability (index)	Peak	0.8	0.65	0.9	0.7	0.6	0.55
	Off-Peak	0.5		0.5		0.5	
Average dwell time(min)	Peak	15	22.5	5	5	35	37.5
	Off-Peak	30		5		40	
Average running speed (mph)	Peak	30	40	43	46.5	70	75
	Off-Peak	50		50		80	

Source: News articles, reports ,Ministry studies,TSRTC,MMTS,HMRL

Step-2: Download DEA frontier analysis

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From online download DEA frontier analysis which would download DEA as an Excel-Add in

- Download
- In Excel go to Options
- Click on Add-ins
- Click on DEA [added to your excel]
- Make sure Solver tab loaded under data tab

Step-3: DEA analysis

- Setup sheet for DEA analysis with format of DMU, Input and Output
- Run DEA by selecting input DMU and output

DMU No.	DMU Name	Efficiency	Passenger load	Service reliability	Average dwell time	Average running speed
1	Bus	0.70000	0.30000	0.30000	0.30000	0.02500
2	Metro	1.00000	0.60000	0.50000	0.36809	0.02068
3	MMTS	0.60000	1.00000	0.22030	0.50000	0.00000
			1.90000	1.02030	1.16809	0.04568

Step:4 – Assessment of efficiency scores

Score	Efficiency or Effectiveness	
1	Efficient /Effective system	
0.6-1	Fairly efficient system	
<0.6	Inefficient system	

Mode of transport	Efficiency score	Efficiency
Bus	0.7	Fairly efficient system

Metro	1	Efficient system
MMTS	0.6	Fairly efficient system

Output of Efficiency analysis

Mode of least performance- Bus systems

Aspect of least performance – Service reliability

3.2 Spatial links of efficiency

Spatial analysis of efficiency is required in order to understand efficiency scenarios on ground.

In this aspect the analysis where each smallest units are required in order analyze an area with respect to various attributes which have an impact on efficiency

Impact attributes of efficiency:

Population: Population has an impact as their demand is responsible for efficient functioning of public transportation.

Land-use: Land use and transportation interaction is **a dynamic process that involves changes over spatial and temporal dimensions between the two systems.** Changes in land use systems can modify the travel demand patterns and induce changes in transportation systems. Various land-use configurations are known to have wide-ranging effects on the dynamics of and within other city components including the transportation system. As well as on functioning of public transportation system.

Figure 50 Inter relation between land use and transport

Source : Landuse integration in Transportation

Road network: Planning of road networks is fundamental for public transportation. Network planning with respect to establishing connections between the nodes through road ways and public transport systems to manage and enhance mobility

Figure 51 Inter-relationship between aspects that impact public transportation

Spatial tools for integration in Arc GIS

Fishnet analysis

The fishnet probabilistic model was developed to characterize the strength distribution based on linked layers

The Create Fishnet tool creates a feature class containing a net of rectangular cells. Creating a fishnet requires three basic sets of information: the spatial extent of the fishnet, the number of rows and columns, and the angle of rotation. There are a variety of ways to specify this information. For example, you may not know the exact number of rows and columns, but you do know that each rectangular cell must be exactly 110 meters by 63 meters and must cover the spatial extent of another feature class.

The tool has 11 parameters, and you should think of these in four distinct groups:

- The spatial extent of fishnet
- The number of rows and columns and height and width of each cell in the fishnet
- The angle of rotation for the fishnet

- Parameters that define the output feature class name and type (polygons or lines) and an optional point dataset containing centroids of each cell

Methods for setting spatial extent

You can set the extent of the fishnet using any of the following methods:

- Enter an existing dataset in the Template Extent parameter. The extent of this dataset will be used as the extent of the fishnet.
- Instead of entering an existing dataset in the Template Extent parameter, supply both the minimum and maximum x- and y-coordinates.
- Enter an origin and opposite corner of the fishnet using the Fishnet Origin Coordinate and Opposite corner of Fishnet parameters.
- Enter an origin, cell size, and number of rows and columns in the Fishnet Origin Coordinate, Cell Size Width, Cell Size Height, Number of Rows, and Number of Columns parameters, respectively.

Setting number of rows and columns

If you have set the extent of the fishnet using one of the first three methods described above, you will need to set the number of rows and columns. There are four methods to specify the number of rows and columns:

- Define the cell width and height with the Cell Size Width and Cell Size Height parameters and leave the Number of Rows and Number of Columns parameters empty or set them to 0. When the tool executes, it calculates the number of rows and columns needed to cover the extent of the fishnet.
- Define the cell width and height as above, but additionally enter the number of rows and columns.
- Define the number of rows and columns by setting the Number of Rows and Number of Columns parameters, and leave the Cell Size Width and Cell Size Height parameters empty or set them to 0. When the tool

executes, it calculates the cell size width and height based on the number of rows and columns and the value of the Opposite corner of Fishnet parameter.

- Define the number of rows and columns as above, but additionally enter a cell size and width. When using this method, the Opposite corner of Fishnet parameter is ignored (in the tool dialog box, the parameter is unavailable). The opposite corner is calculated when the tool runs.

Output feature class

You can choose to create a line or polygon feature class. If you intend to overlay the fishnet with an existing dataset using tools in the Overlay toolset, choose Polygon for the Geometry Type parameter. If you want a fishnet for display purposes, choose Polyline for the Geometry Type parameter. If you have a large number of cells, creating a fishnet with Polygon will be much slower than creating it with Polyline.

You can also create a point feature class by checking the Create Label Points parameter. The points will be located at the center of each cell. If you just want point output and nothing else, choose Polyline for the Geometry Type parameter (because it is the fastest way to construct a fishnet) and check the Create Label Points parameter. After the tool has finished, delete the output line feature class.

In this case :

1. Our extent is HMDA layer applying fishnet for HMDA and Masking the layer with HMDA boundary would result in fishnet inside the boundary of HMDA as shown in the figure

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Figure 52 fishnet

2. The aspects that are to be analyzed

- Population
- Landuse
- Road networks
- transit stations

Population density

Landuse

Road network and stations

Join and Relate

Figure 53 Fishnet analysis

Process of analysis:

Figure 54 Cell analysis

Unit cell based analysis

Each cell individually analyzes the layers in its extent where the value is taken from count in attribute table.

Figure 55 Output of fishnet analysis

Weightage analysis:

Weighting each parameter would infer the extent of impact that these parameters have on efficiency of public transportation network the following are the weights on the scale of 0-1

Tha weightage is major for the population and landuse weights at 0.3 , network weights at 0.2 and presence of a public transit station weights at 0.1

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Parameter	Weight
Population	0.4
Landuse	0.3
network	0.2
Public transit station	0.1

Objective-4 Opinion analysis

4.1 Opinion analysis

Parameters Identification and Scale Design

The selection of performance evaluation parameters and scale design solely depends upon the transit system. The parameters were formulated using all possible demographic and performance variables to capture passenger’s responses

In this study a dual level questionnaire prepared by incorporating satisfaction level with the base line of comparison Expectation level. Hence a constant scale of 5 Likert scale [5] units has been selected which indicates minimum satisfaction and expectation level as 1 and maximum satisfaction and expectation level as 5. The questionnaire was designed to capture the existing satisfaction level for the system and also to capture the expected level of each parameter.

Table 1 Parameters identification

S.no.	Parameters for Bus system	Parameters for MMTS	Parameters for HMRL
1	Cleanliness in the vehicle	Personal Safety onboard	Technical Areas
2	Ventilation in the vehicle	Personal Safety at Station	Automatic Doors

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3	Enough space in the vehicle	Cleanliness of Trains	Security Equipments
4	Vehicle age	Cleanliness of Station	Seating Arrangements
6	Getting a seat	Availability of Seats at Station	Feeder Bus/ Autos
7	Driver and conductor's friendliness	Railway Fare	Convenience
8	Information provision	Information Dessimination at Station	Payment Modes
9	Vehicle availability at peak hours	Timely Information Announcement and Display	Ticket Fare
10	Availability of vehicle after 7 p.m	Ticket Inspection	Announcements
11	Ticket price	Crowding onboard	Maps & Sign Boards
12	Waiting time at the bus stop	Comfort onboard	Query solving
13	Travel time	Frequency of Train	Lost & Found Service
14	Punctuality	Regularity of Train	Safety
15	Vehicle frequency	Complaint Registration	Handling of complaints
16	Driving safety and security	Parameters	Attitude of staff
17	Ambiance/condition of the bus stop	Personal Safety onboard	Atmosphere/ Ambiance in trains or stations.

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19	Passenger's safety	Personal Safety at Station	Cleanliness
20	Absence of noise in the vehicle	Cleanliness of Trains	Parameters
21	Fellow travellers cleanliness	Cleanliness of Station	Technical Areas
22	Passenger politeness	Availability of Seats at Station	Automatic Doors

Data collection:

Data collection is done through following sources

- 1] Google forms
- 2] Direct surveys
- 3] assistance from secondary data of complaint registrations

Sample size:

The initial sample size was determined by the following formula

$$N = \frac{Z^2 pq}{E^2}$$

Where, Z is the normal variate and which has 1.96 for 95% confidence interval

P is the target proportion.in this case we assumed p=0.5

P+q=1, therefore q=.50 and

E is the desired error which is .7

For 250,000 population size and above will require a minimum sample size of 384 respondents at confidence of 95% and margin of error of 5% (G, 2015)

The sample size taken is 784

Characteristics of Respondents

Figure 56 Respondents

Bus	Metro	MMTS	Bus and Metro	Bus and MMTS	MMTS and metro	All modes
239	20	372	78	33	2	20

The totally filled responses which could be dependent for further analysis is given in this table

Bus	Metro	MMTS	Total
350	100	127	577

Figure 57 Respondents

Profession

Vehicle Ownership

Preferred mode of transport

Inference: Majority of respondents are of students shows majority of respondents aged between 18 and 25, profession of the majority (70%) are Students. More than half (55%) of the user have a personal mode (Two wheeler/car) for commuting. Less than half (43 %) passengers are regular commuters with monthly travel card.

Analysis of Data

The processed data was analyzed to find what are the parameters are important and based on which parameters user are rating the system. Important performance analysis, overall satisfaction of the system is calculated.

Important Performance Analysis (IPA)

The performance appraisal of public transport can be carried out using Important Performance Analysis (IPA) is also known as quadrant analysis in order to measure the relationship between user perception and priority In IPA, user satisfaction is translated into Cartesian diagram where two lines perpendicularly divide it into four quadrants shown

Where (Q) represents the average of average scores of level of implementation of all factors and (P) represents the average of average scores of the importance of all factors

Figure 58 cartesian diagram of IPA analysis

The different terms of the Figure 1 are as follows:

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- Point (P) as the middle point of the score level expectations, obtained by dividing the total score of the average level of expectation per respondent each dimension with the existing number of dimensions.
- Point (Q) as the middle point of the performance level score, obtained by dividing the total score of the average level of performance per respondent each dimension with the existing number of dimensions.
- Quadrant 1: The factors that are considered important by the customer but in reality these factors have not been in line with expectations. Attributes that are included in this quadrant should get more attention or repaired so that the performance is increased.
- Quadrant 2: The factors those are included in this quadrant must be maintained because of these quadrant parameters users are using the service, to retain the users these parameters has to be maintained.
- Quadrant 3: The factors that are considered less important by the user but in reality are quite satisfactory. In this quadrant the performance of parameters are more than user's expectations.
- Quadrant 4: The factors that are included in this quadrant considered less important by the customer. The parameters in this quadrant are least prefer by user and their performance also low.

Once the data is collected generation of Performance and importance parameters is required and is processed as follow”

Generating P(performance) and Importance (I) values using the formula

$$P/I = \frac{\sum fx}{N}$$

Where,

f= No. of respondents who specified the grade,

x= Grade,

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N= Number of public transport users

Example:

Parameter	Grade					P
	1	2	3	4	5	
Bus shelter	35	22	32	21	2	$=1 \times 35 + 2 \times 22 + 3 \times 32 + 4 \times 21 + 5 \times 2$

Similarly I (importance) value is calculated using ratings for importance.

Using these I and P values calculating calculating following

Once the P and I values are calculated the graph is generated in IBM SPSS using following steps

1] Install IBM SPSS

2] Enter the values of importance and performance along with the parameters

3] – go to graphs

- go to legacy dialogs

- select simple scatter/ dot

- click on define

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Figure 59 graph generation

4] Under define select X-axis as Performance and Y-axis as Importance click OK.

Figure 60 adding parameters

5] Chart editor window opens with the output

6] edit symbology of symbols

7] From the chart editor add Reference line on X-axis and Y-axis with value of mean

Customer Satisfaction Index (CSI)

Customer Satisfaction Index is a method to determine the level of satisfaction that has been achieved with respect to the service delivered. CSI was proposed by Supranto (1997) [7]. The user satisfaction measured using the average value of the level of expectation and the performance of each service item. The CSI can be calculated by the following steps:

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- Estimation of Mean Important Score (MIS) MIS is the mean value of each variable rate i.e. user satisfaction / expectation.

$$MIS_t = \sum_{t=1}^n \frac{Y_t}{n}$$

Where,

n= no of respondent and

Yt =Expectation value attributes

- Estimation of value of the Mean Satisfaction Score (MSS)
It is the value of an average level of perceived per attributes.

$$MSS_t = \sum_{t=1}^n \frac{X_t}{n}$$

- Estimation of Weight Factor (WFt)
The weight factor is an MIS value per attributes of the sum of all the attributes MIS.

$$WF_t = \frac{MIS_t}{\sum_{t=1}^p MIS_t}$$

- Measurement of Weight Score This weight is the product of WFt with the mean level of service perceived as mean satisfaction score.

$$WS_t = WF_t * MSS_t$$

- Estimation of Customer Satisfaction Index (CSI)

$$CSI = \sum WS_t / 5 \text{ [highest grade]}$$

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Bus systems

S.no.	Parameters	Performance	Importance	WF	WS
1	Cleanliness in the vehicle	2.905714286	2.537142857	4.046479836	11.75791
2	Ventilation in the vehicle	3.451428571	3.151428571	5.026201868	17.34758
3	Enough space in the vehicle	3.017142857	3.374285714	5.381635908	16.23716
4	Vehicle age	2.402857143	2.934285714	4.679881522	11.24509
6	Getting a seat	2.608571429	3.511428571	5.600364548	14.60895
7	Driver and conductor's friendliness	3.128571429	3.257142857	5.194805195	16.25232
8	Information provision	2.788571429	3.588571429	5.723399408	15.96011
9	Vehicle availability at peak hours	3.168571429	3.654285714	5.828206881	18.46709
10	Availability of vehicle after 7 p.m	3.422857143	3.422857143	5.459102301	18.68573
11	Ticket price	2.948571429	3.414285714	5.445431761	16.05624
12	Waiting time at the bus stop	2.997142857	4.114285714	6.561859193	19.66683
13	Travel time	2.857142857	3.271428571	5.217589428	14.9074
14	Punctuality	3.202857143	3.202857143	5.108225108	16.36092
15	Vehicle frequency	3.24	3.24	5.167464115	16.74258
16	Driving safety and security	3.228571429	2.36	3.763955343	12.1522
17	Ambiance/condition of the bus stop	2.92	3.742857143	5.969469127	17.43085
19	Passenger's safety	2.854285714	3.397142857	5.418090681	15.46478
20	Absence of noise in the vehicle	2.614285714	2.434285714	3.882433356	10.14979
21	Fellow travellers cleanliness	3.111428571	2.108571429	3.362952837	10.46359
22	Passenger politeness	3.228571429	1.982857143	3.162451584	10.2102
					300.1673

CSI 60.03346

$$\sum WS/HS$$

HS= highest score =5

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MMTS

Parameters	P	I	WF	WS
Personal Safety onboard	3.188976	3.779528	6.823998	21.76157
Personal Safety at Station	3.393701	3.944882	7.122548	24.1718
Cleanliness of Trains	1.850394	3.96063	7.150981	13.23213
Cleanliness of Station	3.464567	3.874016	6.994598	24.23325
Availability of Seats at Station	3.094488	3.929134	7.094114	21.95265
Railway Fare	3.84252	4.047244	7.307364	28.07869
Information Dessimination at Station	4	4.19685	7.577481	30.30992
Timely Information Announcement and Display	4.007874	4.125984	7.449531	29.85678
Ticket Inspection	3.724409	3.724409	6.724481	25.04472
Crowding onboard	1.314961	4.220472	7.620131	10.02017
Comfort onboard	1.692913	4.125984	7.449531	12.61141
Frequency of Train	3.354331	4.149606	7.492181	25.13125
Regularity of Train	3.503937	3.582677	6.468581	22.6655
Complaint Registration	3.724409	3.724409	6.724481	25.04472
		55.38583		314.1146

CSI 62.82291

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HMRL

Parameters	P	I	WF	WS
Technical Areas	3.58	2.21	3.594665	12.8689
Automatic Doors	3.98	2.07	3.366949	13.40046
Security Equipments	3.81	3.81	6.197137	23.61109
Seating Arrangements	3.96	3.96	6.441119	25.50683
Feeder Bus/ Autos	3.35	3.35	5.448926	18.2539
Convenience	4.16	4.16	6.766428	28.14834
Payment Modes	3.59	3.67	5.969421	21.43022
Ticket Fare	2.98	3.93	6.392323	19.04912
Announcements	3.85	3.85	6.262199	24.10947
Maps & Sign Boards	3.84	3.84	6.245934	23.98439
Query solving	3.96	4.06	6.603774	26.15094
Lost & Found Service	2.54	2.54	4.131425	10.49382
Safety	4	4.1	6.668835	26.67534
Handling of complaints	3.5	3.85	6.262199	21.9177
Attitude of staff	4.02	4.02	6.538712	26.28562
Atmosphere/ Ambiance in trains or stations.	4	4	6.506181	26.02472
Cleanliness	4.06	4.06	6.603774	26.81132
		61.48		374.7222

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Output of IPA analysis

Mode	CSI [Customer satisfaction index]	Quadrant-1 [Areas important but poor service]	Quadrant-2 [Good service]	Quadrant-3 [Not important poor service]	Quadrant-4 [Not important Good service]
Bus	60.03	Information provision Travel time Waiting time Getting a seat Ambience /condition of bustop	Punctuality Availability of vehicle after 7 Enough space in vehicle Passengers safety	Cleanliness of vehicle Absence of noise in vehicles	Frequency Passenger politeness Fellow travellers cleanliness Ventilation Vehicle age
MMTS	62.8	Crowding on board Comfort on board Frequency of train	Information dissemination Cleanliness of station Timely information announcement and display	Cleanliness of trains Availability of seats Personal safety at station Personal safety onboard Fare	Ticket inspection

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Metro	74.9	Ticket fare	Announcements Atmosphere Attitude of staff Cleanliness Convenience Handling complaints Maps and sign boards Payment modes Query solving Safety Seating arrangements Security equipments	Feeder bus Lost and found service	Technical areas Automatic doors
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Arranging quadrant 1 parameters

Information	Travel time	Personal Comfort	Punctuality
1	3	4	1

Variables related to Personal comfort are dominant factors impacting Public transportation

CHAPTER-5
PROPOSALS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

Proposals

Outputs from analysis

Coverage analysis	Efficiency analysis	Opinion analysis
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Area covered under minimum walking distance from public transit station - Zones with large areas from Euclidean allocation 	Mode of transport with least performance – Bus Aspect of least performance – Service reliability	Aspects of personal comfort are required develop

Figure 61 Output from analysis

Key strategy :

The main key strategy in order to carryout with proposals include 2 main aspects

1. Reducing private vehicle
2. Improving performance of public transportation

1.Reducing private vehicles: In order to encourage people towards public transportation discouraging them towards using private vehicles also has a key role. In order to attain this we need to study main aspects which could have a role in burdening private vehicles from instance and from this present scenario we assume following as burden to private vehicle users

- Parking and parking fee
- Fuel costs

Taking these 2 aspects into consideration we need to understand how these aspects would affect or discourage usage of private vehicles and encouragement these burdens would provide to public transportation is to be understood.

Taking similar studies with the similar results from opinion surveys which can be used to assume the similar scenario with respect our case.

Parking fee:

Low parking fees is the one of the reasons that people remain to using private car in city center of Kuala Lumpur, so we propose the possibility of imposing fees on parking within the city centre.

As shown in Fig. 7 the respondents were asked if an increase in parking cost would shift them to public transport. The present cost was assumed to be 40/hour and 88% of respondents will shift if the cost remains 40/hour. 99.5% of respondents would shift to public transport if the cost of parking fee will raise to 50/hour. With 30/hour parking cost, 20% of the responders will shift to public transportation as well. Finally, 7% of respondents have agreed to shift to public transport when parking fees reduced to 20/hour. Increasing parking charges would cause a decrease in term of private vehicles travel into the city-centre which was in concur with other studies

Figure 62 Impact of parking fee

Fuel cost

Figure 63 impact of fuel costs

It can be shown that the difference among the factors that encourage people to shift to public transport. The survey illustrates that the main factor which effect shifting to public transport is increasing fuel cost due to high-shifting percentage when increasing fuel cost above 50 per litre (HAITHAM AL-MSARI1, 2021)

Improving performance of Public transportation

In the 2030 Agenda for Sustainable Development, sustainable transport is mainstreamed across several SDGs and targets, especially those related to food security, health, energy, economic growth, infrastructure, and cities and human settlements. The importance of transport for climate action is further recognized under the UNFCCC - the transport sector will be playing a particularly important role in the achievement of the Paris Agreement, given the fact close to a

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quarter of energy-related global greenhouse gas emissions come from transport and that these emissions are projected to grow substantially in the years to come.

Figure 64 aspects linking to study

Understanding their policy measures of sustainable transport linking to aspects and issues of study

	UN Recommendations	Aspects links with theis	Output links	Recommendations
POLICY DEVELOPMENT AND IMPLEMENTATION	integration vertically among levels of government and horizontally across modes, territories and sectors	Coverage and Efficiency	-Service reliability -Last mile connectivity	- Common travel card - Linkages between modes of transport (public transit stations)
	to ensure equitable access to markets, jobs, education and	Coverage and Efficiency (- Last mile connectivity	-Benchmark proposal for route-

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	other necessities.	trips)	- Personal comfort	planning - Coverage analysis - Last mile connectivity
	Foster an informed, engaged public as a crucial partner in advancing sustainable transport solutions.	Efficiency	- Personal comfort	- Awareness sessions
	Establish monitoring and evaluation frameworks for sustainable transport	Efficiency	- Bus systems improvement - Personal comfort - Service reliability	- ITS for bus transportation
TECHNOLOGICAL INNOVATION	Promote sustainable transport technologies	Efficiency		

Understanding Links of the recommendations with mode specific perspective observed from the IPA analysis

Parameters	Bus
Information provision	ITS for bus system
Travel time	
Waiting time	
Getting a seat	
Ambience /condition of bustop	

Figure 65 Recommendations for bus system

Parameters	MMTS
Crowding on board	Improving frequency and trip planning based on travel demand
Comfort on board	
Frequency of train	

Figure 66 Recommendations for MMTS system

Parameters	Metro
Ticket fare	Efficient use of trip offers and common travel card

Figure 67 Recommendations for Metro

Understanding probability of these initiatives on encouragement of public transportation using opinion analysis

- Refining number of people with related issue which is solved by the given recommendation.
-

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Table 1 Recommendations and proposals

S.No.	Parameters	Recommendation	Features	Significance	Probability test (% of people encouragement)			Impact	Feasibility study
					1 (most likely)	0.5 (neutral)	0 (not likely)		
1.	Coverage and efficiency	Common travel card	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Card that allow citizens to travel across multiple modes of public for commuters in Hyderabad and across the state. enable one card usability in all payment systems 	Improvement in personal comfort (important aspect for shift to private) Experience the efficiency provided by multiple modes. Improve service reliability based on efficiencies provided by multi-modal transport	12.69633508	46.59685864	40.70680628	12% of population would be encouraged	Average impact
					14.65968586	39.13612565	46.20418848	14% of population would be encouraged	Average priority
3.		Benchmark proposal for route planning	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Trip planning algorithm including important parameters. 	Efficiency in trip planning	42.01570681	12.82722513	61.12565445	42% of population would be encouraged	Low priority
4.		Coverage analysis	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Understanding low coverage areas Proposal for bustops 	Improve coverage and solutions for coverage issues	37.43455497	12.95811518	49.60732984	37% of population would be encouraged	High priority
5.		Last mile connectivity	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> App development for last mile connectivity (for more than 500m) integrating with OLA and uber cab services 	Encourage public transportation (as last mile is major aspect for shift to private vehicles)	54.97382199	14.52879581	30.4973822	54% of population would be encouraged	High priority
6.	Efficiency	Awareness sessions	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Awareness of existing schemes and programmes to encourage public 	Encouragement to be aware of new modes of public transport	16.62303665	51.83246073	31.54450262	16% of population would be encouraged	Low Priority
7.		ITS for bus transportation	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> GPS tracking (information dissemination) Passenger count system Monitoring and evaluation frameworks 	Improve service reliability Improve overall bus services [Major step to encourage public]	68.19371728	27.48691099	20.41884817	68% of population would be encouraged	High Priority

Concentrating on High priority measures

- Coverage analysis
- Last mile connectivity
- ITS for bus systems

Coverage analysis: The resultant of the coverage analysis is providing coverage in large zones extracted from euclidean allocation with this provision these areas would has an access to public transportation with means of presence of a transit station [bustop]

- From output of Euclidean allocation identify the zones with large areas

Figure 1 Zones from Euclidean allocation

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- (ii) Understand demographics of the zones
The population densities in these zones are of 200-600 people per sq.km
- (iii) Using fishnet analysis locate proposed bustops with respect to cells of preference and nearest access road

- (iv) Impact of proposed bustop

Zones	Villages	Population densities	Number of villages brought to primary and secondary zones of access
Zone -1	6	200-600 p/sq.km	3
Zone-2	9		3
Zone 3	15		10
Zone 4	8		5

First and last mile connectivity

While India's major transport policies promote public transit systems, multimodal integration, and non-motorised transport (NMT), they are largely silent on the last-mile connectivity aspect.

Figure 69 NUTP structure of priority

City Multi-Modal Transportation App (An Initiative of Xerox Research Center, India)

- Convenient single-source for all public and private mobility options
- Personalized to user's preference (e.g., health, environment, cost, time)
- Unified account-based payments
- Trusted official mobility app of city
- Dynamic re-routing options

Point-to-point trip planning: bridging first and last mile

Pilot launched in Bangalore

Figure 70 Application

Figure 71 system optimization

Strategy of last mile connectivity is

Figure 72 Strategy

Physical integration : Physical integration relates to the aspect of physical connectivity to station which include pedestrian pathways, their conditions and their impact on local environment from the user's perspective .

creating a comfortable walking and cycling environment near stations, and providing infrastructure for e-mobility and shared modes are effective physical interventions to ensure structured last-mile connectivity systems.

The quality of access, while a fraction of the total cost of a public transport system, directly influences its ridership. An efficiently accessible station area will maximise ridership, enable a barrier-free environment, manage parking effectively, provide affordable options to commuters, and create vibrant public spaces. This will help realise the economic development benefits of public transport systems and serve the commuters' needs.

Service integration : Service integration relates other modes of transport which are been integrated for 1st and last mile connectivities these includes modes of transport like autos , electric vehicles

Authorities must enable integrated planning of different modes of transport at station areas. The integration of the various public transport, IPT, and NMT modes with the metros will achieve a better level of service at the stations and improve the connectivity at station areas for the smooth and orderly movement of vehicular and pedestrian traffic. It is also essential to increase the frequency of feeder services and synchronise frequencies and headways with metro rail services to reduce the wait time for commuters while changing transport modes.

The other aspect is that the scope of innovation rises due to this service integration new modes of eco-friendly transport could be encouraged with this means

Institutional integration :

Different agencies regulate last-mile connectivity services. For example, the state transport departments typically govern taxis and auto-rickshaws. Likewise, creating pathways for cycling and walking is under the purview of the urban local bodies, while lighting for the pathway is the mandate of the electricity service provider. The lack of coordination, coupled with each institution

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forming its own rules and procedures, eventually hinders the execution of well-intentioned policies and plans. Metro rail authorities must collaborate with the various service providers to seamlessly integrate all last-mile connectivity plans.

The service providers like OLA, Uber could also be part of institutional integration

Information Integration

Available data and technology solutions will further strengthen the effort to promote last-mile connectivity. Providing real-time service information on the arrival and departure of feeder services will encourage commuters to use public transport modes. For example, an urban bus service should be integrated with metro rail services, such that when a train arrives, it must have bus services available within a short time. Similarly, the integration of fare payments between feeder services and the metro rail and enabling smart cards and cashless transactions for fare payments will make things easier for public transport users.

Example:

Tummoc: Tummoc is a Bengaluru-based mobility startup focussing on multi-mode public transport information and reasonably priced commutation options.

Tummoc provides the most affordable, safe and hassle-free end-to-end commute options by incorporating the public transport network and providing first and last-mile connectivity.

Figure 73 Tummoc app

Intelligent transport systems

An **intelligent transportation system (ITS)** is an advanced application which aims to provide innovative services relating to different modes of transport and traffic management and enable users to be better informed and make safer, more coordinated, and 'smarter' use of transport networks.

Although ITS may refer to all modes of transport, the directive of the European Union 2010/40/EU, made on July 7, 2010, defined ITS as systems in which information and communication technologies are applied in the field of road transport, including infrastructure, vehicles and users, and in traffic management and mobility management, as well as for interfaces with other modes of transport. ITS may be used to improve the efficiency and safety of transport in a number of situations, i.e. road transport, traffic management, mobility, etc. ITS technology is being adopted across the world to increase capacity of busy roads and reduce journey times

Few aspects which suggested for indian cities for Intelligent public transportation systems by UNESCAP

- Automatic Passenger Counters (APC)
- Automatic Vehicle Location (AVL)
- Geographic Information Systems (GIS)
- Signal Priority (SP)

Automatic passenger counts:

An Automated Passenger Counter (APC) is used for public transit vehicles to record boarding and alighting data. This technology can improve comfort zones and also in track ridership.

Automatic vehicle location

AVLS uses Automatic vehicle locator device to enable agency to remotely track the location of a vehicle along with its location attributes like position , weather, traffic etc. and vehicle characteristics like speed, direction etc

Geographic information systems [GIS]

Geographic Information Systems (GISs) is used to manage all types of geographical data.

- The first step of a GIS is to code data collected by

Tracking systems. Thus, the connection of GIS to GPS allows instant mapping and follow up vehicles on their routes.

Signal Prioritization—This technology group includes methods to provide preference or priority to the BRT vehicles. Signal Timing / Phasing and Signal Priority help BRT vehicles minimize delay caused by having to stop for traffic at intersections. Access Control provides the BRT vehicles with unencumbered entrance to and exit from their facilities. All prioritization for BRT vehicles reduces travel delay and increases reliability of the BRT operation

Figure 74 ITS for Bus systems

Summary and conclusion

From the research problem of increase in private vehicles which is affecting both environment and traffic scenarios on ground we came up with a hypothesis that improving coverage and efficiency of public transportation would be an initiative to reduce the usage of private vehicles

In this aspect we studied coverage in the study area and analyzed it using Euclidean tools from which we got the least covered area and with respect to efficiency we analyzed them using a technique of DEA [data envelopment analysis] which gave us the output of efficiency scores of each mode of transport with respect to our study. and opinion analysis is done with IPA analysis technique which gave us the output as public comfort aspect needs improvement for improving public encouragement

Using these outputs from the series of analysis the proposals are being made in correlation to Sustainable transport policy recommendations through which a sustainable perspective of improving coverage and efficiency is being achieved

Finally approximate probability of people willing to use the public transportation using these initiatives is being assessed which showed up that my hypothesis is true that there would be encouragement of public in using public transportation facilities if the efficiency and coverage is being improved in the study area

Figure 75 conclusion

Annexure-I

Survey format

Created in: Google forms

1.Name _____

2. Age

- 18-25
- 25-35
- 36-45
- 46-55
- 56-65
- Above 65

3. Profession

- Employee
- Unemployed
- House wife
- Pensioner
- Student
- Others

4. Vehicle ownership

- No Vehicle
- Cycle
- Two-wheeler
- Four wheeler

5. Your preferred mode of Public transport

- Bus
- HMRL
- MMTS

6. Trip purpose

- Work
- Recreation
- Social
- Education

7. Mode used for First and last mile connectivity

- Walk
- Private vehicle
- Auto

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- Cab services

8. Ticket type

- One-way ticket
- 2-way ticket
- Monthly travel card

9. Rate your present satisfaction levels on following aspects when using a public transport

Mode of Bus

Parameter	Grade				
	1	2	3	4	5
Cleanliness in the vehicle	1	2	3	4	5
Ventilation in the vehicle	1	2	3	4	5
Enough space in the vehicle	1	2	3	4	5
Vehicle age	1	2	3	4	5
Getting a seat	1	2	3	4	5
Driver and conductor's friendliness	1	2	3	4	5
Information provision	1	2	3	4	5
Vehicle availability at peak hours	1	2	3	4	5
Availability of vehicle after 7 p.m	1	2	3	4	5
Ticket price	1	2	3	4	5
Waiting time at the bus stop	1	2	3	4	5
Travel time	1	2	3	4	5
Punctuality	1	2	3	4	5
Vehicle frequency	1	2	3	4	5
Driving safety and security	1	2	3	4	5
Ambiance/condition of the bus stop	1	2	3	4	5
Passenger's safety	1	2	3	4	5
Absence of noise in the vehicle	1	2	3	4	5
Fellow travellers cleanliness	1	2	3	4	5
Passenger politeness	1	2	3	4	5

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Mode of MMTS

Parameters	Grade				
	1	2	3	4	5
Personal Safety onboard	1	2	3	4	5
Personal Safety at Station	1	2	3	4	5
Cleanliness of Trains	1	2	3	4	5
Cleanliness of Station	1	2	3	4	5
Availability of Seats at Station	1	2	3	4	5
Railway Fare	1	2	3	4	5
Information Dessimination at Station	1	2	3	4	5
Timely Information Announcement and Display	1	2	3	4	5
Ticket Inspection	1	2	3	4	5
Crowding onboard	1	2	3	4	5
Comfort onboard	1	2	3	4	5
Frequency of Train	1	2	3	4	5
Regularity of Train	1	2	3	4	5
Complaint Registration	1	2	3	4	5

Mode of HMRL

Parameters	Grade				
	1	2	3	4	5
Technical Areas	1	2	3	4	5
Automatic Doors	1	2	3	4	5
Security Equipments	1	2	3	4	5
Seating Arrangements	1	2	3	4	5
Feeder Bus/ Autos	1	2	3	4	5
Convenience	1	2	3	4	5
Payment Modes	1	2	3	4	5
Ticket Fare	1	2	3	4	5
Announcements	1	2	3	4	5
Maps & Sign Boards	1	2	3	4	5
Query solving	1	2	3	4	5
Lost & Found Service	1	2	3	4	5
Safety	1	2	3	4	5
Handling of complaints	1	2	3	4	5
Attitude of staff	1	2	3	4	5
Atmosphere/ Ambiance in trains or stations.	1	2	3	4	5
Cleanliness	1	2	3	4	5

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10.. Rate your present Importance levels on following aspects when using a public transport [How important are the following aspects]

Mode of Bus

Parameter	Grade				
	1	2	3	4	5
Cleanliness in the vehicle	1	2	3	4	5
Ventilation in the vehicle	1	2	3	4	5
Enough space in the vehicle	1	2	3	4	5
Vehicle age	1	2	3	4	5
Getting a seat	1	2	3	4	5
Driver and conductor's friendliness	1	2	3	4	5
Information provision	1	2	3	4	5
Vehicle availability at peak hours	1	2	3	4	5
Availability of vehicle after 7 p.m	1	2	3	4	5
Ticket price	1	2	3	4	5
Waiting time at the bus stop	1	2	3	4	5
Travel time	1	2	3	4	5
Punctuality	1	2	3	4	5
Vehicle frequency	1	2	3	4	5
Driving safety and security	1	2	3	4	5
Ambiance/condition of the bus stop	1	2	3	4	5
Passenger's safety	1	2	3	4	5
Absence of noise in the vehicle	1	2	3	4	5
Fellow travellers cleanliness	1	2	3	4	5
Passenger politeness	1	2	3	4	5

Mode of MMTS

Parameters	Grade				
	1	2	3	4	5
Personal Safety onboard	1	2	3	4	5
Personal Safety at Station	1	2	3	4	5
Cleanliness of Trains	1	2	3	4	5
Cleanliness of Station	1	2	3	4	5
Availability of Seats at Station	1	2	3	4	5
Railway Fare	1	2	3	4	5
Information Dessimination at Station	1	2	3	4	5
Timely Information Announcement and Display	1	2	3	4	5
Ticket Inspection	1	2	3	4	5

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Crowding onboard	1	2	3	4	5
Comfort onboard	1	2	3	4	5
Frequency of Train	1	2	3	4	5
Regularity of Train	1	2	3	4	5
Complaint Registration	1	2	3	4	5

Mode of HMRL

Parameters	Grade				
	1	2	3	4	5
Technical Areas	1	2	3	4	5
Automatic Doors	1	2	3	4	5
Security Equipments	1	2	3	4	5
Seating Arrangements	1	2	3	4	5
Feeder Bus/ Autos	1	2	3	4	5
Convenience	1	2	3	4	5
Payment Modes	1	2	3	4	5
Ticket Fare	1	2	3	4	5
Announcements	1	2	3	4	5
Maps & Sign Boards	1	2	3	4	5
Query solving	1	2	3	4	5
Lost & Found Service	1	2	3	4	5
Safety	1	2	3	4	5
Handling of complaints	1	2	3	4	5
Attitude of staff	1	2	3	4	5
Atmosphere/ Ambiance in trains or stations.	1	2	3	4	5
Cleanliness	1	2	3	4	5

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